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Accounting Software Used in the Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration

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The Researchers

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ABSTRACT

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This study investigated the commonly used accounting software in the workplace to ascertain its importance for the BSA curriculum and to provide recommendations on which accounting software should be taught at Palawan State University. This research was conducted within the context of Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus, located at Tiniguiban Heights, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan in February 2025. Survey questionnaires were disseminated through social media channels of graduates of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) of Palawan State University, identifying which accounting software they use at their profession, its level of difficulty in terms of usage, their mode of learning these, and the advantage of its usage in the real world. The questionnaire also determined whether or not accounting software should be included in the BSA curriculum and the reasons for this recommendation. Information from 33 respondents of the total population amounted to valuable insights about accounting software through their lenses. Results established that graduates of BSA at Palawan State University use Microsoft Excel, QuickBooks, and Oracle NetSuite at work, where learning difficulty varies as to prior exposure and training. Follow-ups revealed that some accounting software was commonly used outside the Philippines. QuickBooks is popular in the United States, while Oracle NetSuite and Xero are prevalent in Australia. Despite the availability of accounting software aligned with Philippine Financial Reporting Standards and Philippine Accounting Standards, its usage among graduates remains minimal. Instead, Microsoft Excel is frequently adapted as a makeshift accounting system. Findings suggest that accounting software should be taught as early as the college level to maximize exposure to what is used in the workplace. Recommendations include enhancing the current related course to cater not only to basic Microsoft Excel functions but also to integrating accounting software training to BSA students, enhancing real-world skills, and gaining adequate practical exposure to industry-standard tools through coursework and hands-on learning.

Keywords: *accounting software, workplace integration, BSA curriculum, Palawan State University, Microsoft Excel, QuickBooks, Oracle NetSuite, Xero, Philippine financial reporting standards (PFRS), Philippine Accounting Standards (PAS), industry-standard tools, survey questionnaires, graduates' insights, learning difficulty, prior exposure and training, mode of learning, real-world application, curriculum enhancement, hands-on learning*

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter discussed the evolving landscape of accounting education, where the increasing prominence of accounting software demands a deeper understanding of how graduates perceive and utilize these tools. This study focused on the accounting software used by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University from 2016 to 2020 in their workplace and the advantages of using it. The findings of this study provided a basis for introducing core software skills into the BSA curriculum, bridging the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the accounting profession. By responding to this need, graduates will be better prepared to meet the technological advancements that are shaping the modern accounting workplace.

Background of the Study

Accounting software is a computer program and a tool that is essential for many businesses, especially in modern times. In a usual sense, accounting software is defined as a computer program or system that involves the collection, storage, organization, management, tracking, and reporting of the financial transactions of the entity (Kenton, 2020), allowing organizations and firms to keep a detailed record of their day-to-day transactions, income, and expenses, and to assist in preparing financial reports. According to the study by Nicolau (2006, *as cited in* Abdullah *et al.*, 2020), accounting software provided results that are more accurate and reliable than traditional accounting methods, and it is less likely to make errors. Unlike the old traditional way of using journals and worksheets, the use of accounting software helped businesses record and analyze large transactions easily, store numerous amounts of data, reduce errors, and

improve the efficiency of an organization or larger firms (*see Arcega et al., 2015*). In Lipa City, Batangas alone, 64.29% of the existing SMEs at that time were using computerized accounting software for their business, with QuickBooks being used by 17.46% of the total respondents who use computerized accounting software (*Arcega et al., 2015*).

Considering the advantages accounting software offers, accountants today are assisted in recording and reporting financial transactions of a firm. With accounting software, accountants have easy access to the financial information of an entity, easing the process of calculating its gross income and preparing financial statements. However, keeping up with the new technology is not that easy, and this also applies to accountants. Nowadays, accountants who are skilled and knowledgeable in cloud-based accounting software are in higher demand than those who do not have the skills. As more work and transactions are being automated, accountants need to develop their skills and adapt to the use of technology in assessing and analyzing financial reports or data of the company.

This gradual shift is relevant in Palawan, as businesses are thriving from left to right, and it is certain that more and more businesses will rise from the ground, with their driving force being to attain profitability by taking advantage of the desires of the customers. With the advancements in technology happening in real-time, it is of great importance that Certified Public Accountants (CPA) need to have a thorough understanding of accounting software and take advantage of its effectiveness to remain competitive in the workplace.

The Palawan State University (PSU) is one of the only two institutions that offer a Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) in the whole of Palawan, alongside the

Holy Trinity University (HTU). At its current state, the prospectus of the said program consists of little immersion in the diverse accounting software in the Philippines. This is understandable, as accounting software and related concepts were yet to be included in its board examinations. Currently, the Table of Specifications for CPA examinations include Financial Accounting and Reporting (FAR), Advanced Financial Accounting and Reporting (AFAR), Management Advisory Services (MAS), Taxation, Auditing, and Regulatory Framework in Business Transactions (RFBT). Still, it does not include questions related to Information Technology. This exclusion leaves a potential gap in the practical readiness of new accountants entering the field (*see* Meyer, 2021).

As the studies by Arcega *et al.* and Nicolau date back to decades past, new information is of impending cruciality to build and contribute to the existing sphere of knowledge for the betterment of the understanding in this field. What is the state of accounting today, as we speak? What has evolved from before that we know of today? Thus, this study made by the researchers is of great interest to the field as it specifically focused on the accounting software commonly used by the BSA graduates from Palawan State University during the years 2016 to 2020, and that could help improve the curriculum when it comes to the use of accounting software. This study provided interesting and valuable insights as to what recommendations the researchers can provide for the betterment of the accounting profession, ensuring that future accountants are well-prepared for whatever numbers are thrown at them, keeping up with the ever-evolving demands of this profession.

Statement of the Problem

The impact of technology is undeniable; the adoption of these tools in specific regions, such as Palawan, may vary. This study examined the use of accounting software by those who graduated from BSA at PSU and its relevance to their careers. By understanding how these graduates utilize software skills in their workplaces, we can identify the most relevant software programs for integration into the BSA curriculum, bridging the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the modern accounting workplace. Primarily, this study sought to identify the accounting software commonly used by the BSA graduates from Palawan State University during the years 2016 to 2020, and that could help improve the curriculum when it comes to the use of accounting software.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of BSA graduates in terms of:
 - a. year graduated; and
 - b. field practicing the profession?
2. What accounting software(s) are commonly used by the BSA graduates in their workplace?
3. What are the specific advantages that BSA graduates have in using accounting software in their workplaces?
4. Which accounting software programs are most applicable for integration in the BSA curriculum at Palawan State University?

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to bridge the gap between academic preparation and the evolving demands of the accounting profession by examining the use of accounting software by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Identify the profile of BSA graduates from Palawan State University in terms of:
 - a. year graduated; and
 - b. field practicing the profession;
2. Determine the most commonly used accounting software programs among BSA graduates;
3. Assess the specific advantages that BSA graduates experience in using accounting software in their workplaces; and
4. Develop recommendations for the integration of accounting software programs into the BSA curriculum at Palawan State University.

Significance of the Study

By understanding the actual accounting software used by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University and the benefits they experience, this study provided a foundation for integrating essential software skills into the BSA curriculum.

Thus, the following sectors will stand to gain from this study:

Students: This study provided current accountancy students with insights into the importance of acquiring accounting software proficiency as part of their education. It may encourage them to engage in developing technological competencies to meet workplace demands effectively.

Graduates: This research may utilize them to reflect on their own proficiency and evaluate their knowledge, which they might use in their professional performance. This may also highlight areas for potential skill enhancement.

Educational Institutions: This research could be their guide in producing graduates ready to take on technological demands at their workplaces based on its accounting curriculum. This could make some reviews of whether their programs currently meet the needs of the industry and take necessary steps to improve the readiness of students.

Certified Public Accountants: This study gave an overview of the relationship between accounting software skills and workplace performance. This study may be useful for CPAs to assess their accounting software proficiency in their practice areas. By keeping the skills of Certified Public Accountants up to date with global trends, this study would also greatly benefit the accounting sector. Furthermore, the quality of their services will be positively impacted. Organizations and a number of interested parties—but most importantly, the general public—will therefore have more confidence in financial reports that are issued.

Employers and Business Organizations: This may provide them with significant findings that will assist organizations in planning effective training programs or tools that address the gaps to meet industry-standard software proficiency.

Future Researchers: They may benefit from this research as a reference to support their information or future studies.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed to assess the relationship between the professional characteristics (graduation year and field of practice) of Palawan State University (PSU) Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from 2016 to 2020 and their use of accounting software in their professional practice. The research focused on individuals who have completed a BSA degree from PSU and graduated within the above-mentioned years. The BSA graduates from 2016 to 2020 numbered 107 in total. However, only 33 respondents were able to give response from the structured questionnaire. Reasons include busy schedules due to the fact that they are already in their professional work, privacy concerns, confidentiality doubts and lack of interest as some may not find the topic relevant or interesting. The primary variables examined include the commonly used accounting software and its relevance to current professional practices in the field.

This study focused on the use of accounting software in professional practice. The study did not focus on other types of software, such as general-purpose spreadsheets or other business applications, in the workplace. Furthermore, the research excluded BSA graduates from other educational institutions, those who graduated from PSU outside the above timeframe, and BSA graduates of PSU who are currently working on a part-time basis. This delimitation ensured a focused analysis of PSU graduates within the specified timeframe and on their use of accounting software in their professional practice, providing more accurate insights into the relationship between their professional characteristics and their software usage.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined for a clearer understanding of the variables of the study:

Academe

In accounting, this sector refers to those solely focused on education and innovation.

Accounting Software

This refers to any computer program used by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates in their accounting roles to perform tasks such as financial record-keeping, financial reports generation, accounts payable and receivable management, inventory tracking, payroll processing, and invoice creation.

Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA)

This is an academic program that is designed to prepare students for careers in accounting, auditing, taxation, and financial management.

Certified Public Accountants (CPA)

These are professionals who graduated with a bachelor's degree of Science in Accountancy, who took the licensure examinations and are deemed qualified by the Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) of the Philippines.

Curriculum Integration

This is a process of integrating particular learning content or skills into the curriculum. It deals with the integration of accounting software skills in the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) curriculum in relation to the demands of the industry.

Graduates

These refer to the individuals who have completed the degree of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) degree at Palawan State University.

Government Sector

This sector prioritizes the proper handling of funds and preparation of budget while recording and managing transactions incurred by the government and its units.

Perception

This refers to a state of understanding and insight towards a particular subject.

Private Sector

These are firms that perform their profession for businesses, organizations, or companies.

Public Sector

This refers to firms that offer their audit, consultation, and tax preparation services to the general public.

Respondents

These are the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University who were surveyed in this study and are currently working on a full-time basis in the government, private, public, and academic sectors, respectively.

Software Proficiency

This refers to the ability to use computer-based accounting software packages efficiently. It is considered the extent to which the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates are applying in their work such tools or packages.

Workplace Effectiveness

This refers to the capacity of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately through accounting software.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The objective of this chapter is to review the literature and studies from foreign and local sources related to the study of the researchers at hand, providing the researchers an insight into what past studies have covered in this field and identifies what areas are left for future researchers to delve into. This will also tackle the current theories and practices that are relevant and existing in this sphere of study and which part requires further thorough understanding. At the end of this chapter, the researchers will lay down the synthesis of the conceptual framework that shall serve as both the summary of key findings and the basis of this study.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Year of Graduation

To better understand how the graduation date of accounting graduates is a significant factor in finding out the workplace of the said graduates in relation to accounting software, the researchers will refer to other sources for comparison.

Sainio and Virtanen (2016) noted in their study that Finnish students “worked on average 3.98 years during their studies”. They noted that their professionalism improved during their time at work, even though they were not working in line with their chosen program. In comparison, most, if not all, of the earlier graduates of Accountancy are likely to be introduced to accounting software far earlier than newer ones, suggesting that earlier graduates know the trade first before the newer graduates, and this should be true with accounting software. Still, this cannot be the case, as there could be cultural and economic differences between Finnish students and Filipino graduates. Nonetheless, one point stands out from this study. There is a correlation

between the experience of an individual and their performance at work, regardless of what kind of work it is, which brings this review to De Souza-Talarico *et al.* (2007) and the psychological side of things.

The results of De Souza-Talarico *et al.* showed a direct correlation between the education level and the working performance of an individual. One reason education is “frequently found for at least some tests of neurophysical functioning” is its relation to socioeconomic status and its “brain reserve capacity in early life” (Mortimer & Graves, 1993, *as cited in* De Souza-Talarico *et al.*). Following this study, there is a possibility that fresher graduates of the said program may have a better grasp of accounting software in the workplace than others.

Meanwhile, Faught *et al.* (2016) focused their study on how well students under a “supercourse” (i.e., an accelerated course of study) excel compared to students under a traditional course in retaining their knowledge. While their research focuses on the comparison of the two courses of study offered at Brock University, their results show a decline in knowledge retention as months go by, in both the *supercourse* and the traditional course; regardless of the mode of learning imposed on students, retention of far better than that learned months before. Contradictory, “few studies actually support the assumption that almost all knowledge learned in school [. . .] will be lost in the course of a few years” (Custers, 2010). One study from Custers showed positive knowledge retention before knowledge lay a flat line, or “permanently retrievable”. Knowledge loss is found at a later stage, citing probable age-related causes.

In addition to the above context, trends among software programs are also an interesting take; D&V Philippines (2015), for example, shared that FreshBooks, QuickBooks, Kashoo, Outright, and Xero were among the most commonly used cloud

accounting software in business during 2016. Common reasons include enhanced functionalities and user friendliness among small businesses. Outright did not make it to the list given by Kahlid (2017), while additional software programs like Zoho Books, Wave Accounting, Sage One, FinancialForce, FreeAgent, and ClearBooks waved flags at the dawn of the year. By 2018, however, Cooke (2018) included Financial Edge NXT, Avalara AvaTax, and Abila MIP Fund Accounting to the roster list; FinancialForce, FreeAgent, and ClearBooks did not gain enough user popularity. In 2018, as cited in one report (Association of Chartered Certified System Accountants, 2024), 35% of businesses upgrading accounting software came from Intuit QuickBooks. The rest are from QuickBooks-derived applications—Pro, Online, Enterprise, and Premier—and Sage 50. This information emphasizes the strong market presence of QuickBooks and its status as a base platform from which companies look to more sophisticated alternatives, which goes on in the following years. 2019 was a high time for QuickBooks, Xero, and Sage50, alongside Zoho Books, Wave Accounting, and Oracle (Profit Matters, 2019), as recommendations for those software became highly prevalent and widespread. Xero, QuickBooks, FreshBooks, Sage, and Wave Accounting became popular in 2020 (BooksTime, 2020).

Altogether, their findings correlate education and work and how they affect each other, where time is a significant factor in the quality of work exerted. With that in mind, it is unsurprising that the researchers aimed to assess when the Bachelor of Science in Accounting graduates graduated and compare it with how well they learned the needed accounting software skills. Fresh graduates may have better theoretical knowledge, but earlier graduates could have stronger practical expertise in various accounting software used in the workplace. With the addition of the popular software programs from 2016 to 2020, this study can see which were primarily used by BSA graduates in Palawan

State University and compare them with the abovementioned standards, leading the researchers to go beyond simple demographic profiling to determine what has become of them, supporting the researchers in deciding which are the accounting software graduates commonly use, and whether or not the Accountancy program would benefit from the existence of such a curriculum, as the year of graduation will classify the respondents as to how well-versed they were with the accounting software used in the workplace.

Use of Accounting Software in Different Sectors

With the accounting profession branching out to four different sectors, i.e., the public sector, the private sector, the government, and the academe, it is important to ask the underlying question: *How is accounting software used in different sectors of the accounting profession?* Hence, this part of the review serves as the backbone of the interactions of these sectors with accounting-related information and communication technologies (ICT) over the years.

The continuous development of ICT has been a significant advantage in many companies and the accounting profession. Development has been a major factor in an efficient and reliable accounting system and in improving the overall performance of an organization (Taiwo & Edwin, 2016). Studies show an impact on the private sector, including micro, small, and medium enterprises. Proficiency in accounting software improves the handling of business transactions (e.g., generating reports of financial statements, cash flows, or various budgets) and overall effectiveness and efficiency of accountants, making it quicker and more accurate than traditional accounting systems (Thottoli, 2020; Johari *et al.*, 2022; Paramitha & Juliarsa, 2021; Agha *et al.*, 2020; *see Hamza et al.*, 2023 and Arcega *et al.*, 2015).

ICT also shaped the efficiency and effectiveness of the government sector. In one study, the full digitalization of the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) on the collection of revenue and payment eased the filing process, making it faster for taxpayers. Results show a similar pattern to those in the private sector. In addition, the digitalization reduced the administrative burden of government employees through electronic invoices and e-reminders for overdue payments, providing quality enhancements while decreasing operating expenses (Morales, 2024). This digitalization opened trust, helping taxpayers manage their transactions with accuracy and in line with BIR regulations (QNE Software Philippines, 2019).

The academic sector also benefits from ICT. Boulianne (2024) showed that, while manual computation provides greater knowledge depth for the students to understand each step in the documentation and recording process of the accounting system, the use of accounting software increases the knowledge and competencies of the students in handling accounting problems or cycles, and provides hands-on experience in real-life business setups. In addition, accounting software usage improves the curriculum by having the students experience more hands-on activities and practice using tools that accountants use in companies. These make lessons more practical, easier to understand, and help students see how accounting works in the real world.

Even the public sector receives benefits from the existence of ICT. To Đurović and Dečman (2024), there was a positive correlation between the digital transformation in accounting firms and recognized advantages of digital business processes. The majority of the respondents agreed that digitalization has improved their business process, and the benefit of digitalization outweighs the cost. In addition, the study shows that firms with more digital processes perform better in efficiency, speed, and

workflow management, saving time, lessening errors, and having better data management.

Overall, their findings show that adopting accounting software helps improve the overall performance of not only the accountants but also the organization. Using accounting software allows businesses and even the government to enhance the quality of work, making it faster, easier, and more accurate. Thus, it is essential to inquire in which sector the Bachelor of Science and Accountancy graduates fall. Knowing which sector will help the researchers ascertain patterns as to the usage of different accounting software used in the workplace, providing insights on which software should be given priority in the integration into the university curricula.

Commonly Used Accounting Software

Nugrahani (2025) provides an extensive overview of the most popular accounting software in the Philippines. Businesses increasingly use accounting software to streamline processes such as payments tracking, inventory management, and payroll generation, with reduced errors, easier processes, and better decision-making. Success is dependent on selecting the correct accounting software. Businesses must carefully weigh their specific requirements and regulatory needs when choosing software. Although the market has a lot to choose from, there are some software programs that are especially well-liked among Philippine companies.

Accounting software programs Nurgahani listed that are known to be the most used accounting software in the Philippines include:

- **QuickBooks.** The Milestone Team (2024) argues that QuickBooks is the most recognized and popular accounting software, especially among SMEs, and based on surveys, around 50% of accountants use this mainly because of its

extremely high functionality, making it more easily integrated with other tools. Comparatively, about 80% of accountants in small businesses prefer QuickBooks. Tagamolila (2023), Quickbook has a cloud option and an offline version and is preferred by businesses working in one location only since it allows high customization and advanced features. Due to its security and complexity, it has remained the choice for companies whose accounting needs are more diverse than others. QuickBooks Online integrates cloud-based technology with extremely vast capabilities in service offerings of ultra-high customizability. QuickBooks Online allows the company to work with others, leverage other software or applications besides it, provide an end-to-end experience for finance and accounting professionals working through tasks, and enable the user to store financial data in a secure manner. However, Canes (n.d.) mentioned that QuickBooks has limitations, including weak reporting, inventory control issues, system crashes, large file size problems, and limited professional support. It lacks invoice design, requires integration with other systems (risking errors), and makes financial records vulnerable to tampering.

- **Xero.** According to Tagamolila (2023), Xero is a widely used cloud-based accounting software among finance and accounting professionals, especially in the Philippines, due to its user-friendly features, including cash-based and accrual-based bookkeeping support. By its nature, it allows users to work in real-time remotely, which is very efficient because the accounting team can work anywhere, anytime. Because Xero constantly updates its software, even recently introducing an AI feature, it became one of the most trusted software to automate accounting tasks. In an analysis by Goringe (2023), The learning curve of Xero is quite manageable. However, it may take time for users to grasp

its full functionality and use it optimally, requiring proper training and familiarization. Xero also recently raised its prices and removed built-in payroll. Its requisition, purchase, and inventory features are also basic, wherein companies with advanced inventory needs may require additional plugins. Advanced features such as expense claims, projects, and multi-currency support are only available in the highest-priced plan. Xero also lacks a built-in debtor chasing tool and does not support Exchange Traded Products (ETPs), which requires separate software for businesses with significant ETP investments. Performance issues with heavy online activity or high PayPal transaction volume may also arise. Lastly, some users have reported slow customer support, prompting businesses to prepare to use all available resources for assistance.

- **HashMicro.** A BIR-approved accounting software popular in the Philippines that focuses on financial processes such as asset handling, depreciation, budgeting, and tax calculation according to the local regulations. Technology Evaluation Centers (n.d.) mentioned that it requires technical expertise and time for installation and setup, and can take extra developer resources to transition to new business requirements. Businesses must also invest in appropriate servers, security software, and adequate bandwidth capacity. The large initial software license acquisition can also delay the ROI.
- **QNE Accounting Software.** QNE Software is an offline accounting tool designed for businesses in the Philippines and other Southeast Asian countries, which helps track finances, invoicing, stock management, and Philippine tax-compliant sales tracking. QNE Software Philippines (2023) stated that the cons of their software are that users are entirely responsible for setups and backups because of its offline operations. offline systems limit real-time collaboration,

which may not be the best option, especially for companies requiring several users to share and update financial information. Also, there might be periodic fees for updates and support, making it critical to consider the total cost of ownership over time.

- **FreshBooks Online.** FreshBooks is an accounting software for freelancers, small business owners, and entrepreneurs. It simplifies managing payments, expenses, and financial reports through a more advanced double-entry accounting system. Moreover, Tagamolila (2023) stated that FreshBooks is simple and has a user-friendly interface requiring little to no experience in accounting. However, according to Whiz Consulting (2023), FreshBooks is unsuitable for large companies with complex financial needs, especially those requiring advanced reporting or invoicing features. There is also a restriction on the number of users in the entry-level plans, with a limit of 5 to 50 clients.
- **Wave Accounting System Software.** Wave Accounting offers basic accounting features such as income and expense tracking, tailored sales taxes, and generic accounting reports, making it an excellent option for freelancers and entrepreneurs starting. In a review by Crawford (2025), however, Wave Accounting has no inherent third-party integrations or advanced features like mileage tracking, time-tracking, and inventory management that can enhance functionality. Live support is also unavailable unless subscribed to the Pro plan or some other paid offering, and audit trails are lacking.
- **Sap.** Sap is a financial accounting software designed to support small and medium sized businesses. It helps track income and expenses, and generate financial reports. SAP extends beyond simple accounting functions, providing powerful features for overseeing inventory, managing projects, facilitating

manufacturing operations, and much more. Although SAP shares similarities with QuickBooks, it stands apart in several ways. Its pricing is significantly higher—starting at nine times the cost of QuickBooks but that extra investment grants businesses access to expanded functionality. With SAP, companies can efficiently handle human resources, utilize business intelligence tools, and take advantage of a more sophisticated interface tailored for larger enterprises (Casual, 2023).

- **Zoho Books.** Zoho Books is a cloud-based accounting software that integrates with other Zoho services, offering tools for invoicing, inventory, and project tracking modules, making it easy to manage the finances, and can even be used with other Zoho applications to manage different parts of the business, like sales or customer service making it suitable for managing multiple business aspects. Berner (2024) stated that Zoho Books demands coding skills for full automation capabilities, which might be difficult for business owners lacking technical expertise. The transaction and user limits might discourage high-volume businesses. Furthermore, project accounting and inventory management are available only in premium plans.
- **Sage Intacct.** Sage Intacct is a powerful accounting software designed for larger businesses with complex financial needs, offering deep data analysis and detailed reporting. It is AICPA-endorsed with GAAP and HIPAA compliance. Cargas (2025) reviewed the price of Sage Intacct, although expensive, it is in line with comparable mid-market solutions. Its cost reflects its growth potential and specialized modules, though extra fees for training and support may apply. It also requires third-party tools for manufacturing, inventory, HR/payroll, or time tracking. While Sage Intacct is highly customizable during setup, post-

implementation changes are complex due to the need for GAAP compliance, requiring developer or reseller support for adjustments. Although some users favor complete control, others find comfort in handing technical tasks to specialists.

- **Oracle NetSuite Cloud.** Oracle is an accounting software solution for companies. It has financial procedures modules, accounts payable and accounts receivable modules, CRM, and e-commerce business with complete business intelligence functionalities, indicating that this program has a premium price compared to similar programs. It is not free and does not include a built-in payroll feature.
- **Kashoo.** Kashoo is a cloud-based accounting software that is easy to use and an affordable option for smaller businesses and freelancers. It allows users to create invoices, manage expenses, track transactions, print reports on any computer, and has an option to upgrade for more advanced features. Belevska (2024) stressed that Kashoo has limited integration options, restraining its usefulness for some users. It lacks advanced features such as sophisticated reporting, complete invoice customization, and inventory control. It is also not scalable for growing businesses.
- **MYOB.** MYOB is an accounting platform popular for small businesses and retailers in the Philippines. It specializes in bookkeeping and tax management and features invoice tracking, expense tracking, taxation, GST management, and payroll processing. According to Business Oasis (2024), MYOB has limited third-party integration capabilities, limiting the flexibility of the software to suit unique bookkeeping requirements. Its interface can also be overwhelming for

new users, and some features are only available on desktop or cloud versions, limiting access for bookkeepers who work for other businesses.

- **EasyFS.** EasyFS is a cloud-based accounting software designed for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses (MSMEs), helping companies track their sales, inventory, expenses, and financial reports. It is fully compliant with the Philippine regulations, making it a good option for businesses that must stay on top of their tax obligations. However, EasyFS may not fully address the more intricate and demanding requirements of larger companies.
- **JuanTax.** JuanTax is a Philippine accounting and tax professional software program. It automates tax return filing processes, updating itself about local tax laws. It is for Filipino businesses, accountants, and bookkeepers who require automatic tax return preparation and e-filing, but lack quick customer support, the option to alter postings, and a difficult learning curve.
- **AccountEdge.** It is a desktop-based solution that offers a wide range of features, from payroll to inventory management. It is a good option for small and medium-sized businesses that need a comprehensive accounting tool. This software offers limited reporting capabilities, which might impede intricate financial analysis. It is also expensive, particularly for small firms, and involves cumbersome integration with other systems, thus making flawless workflow challenging.
- **Tipalti.** Tipalti is an accounting software that automates tasks involved in managing payments, procurements, expenses, and accounts payable for businesses. However, the software is expensive for small businesses despite having limited customization features and slow customer support response times.

- **Sage 50.** A desktop-based accounting solution for small and medium-sized businesses, such as construction, manufacturing, and distribution, offering cloud connectivity and integration with Microsoft 365 tools like Excel and Outlook. However, it is only available on Windows platforms, and no mobile apps, limiting flexibility. Some user interface components also feel outdated, potentially impacting user experience and navigation.
- **Odoo Accounting.** This accounting software integrates with other Odoo modules for sales, inventory, and customer relationship management, offering customizable features for business needs. Advanced features, however, require the paid enterprise version, restricting access for companies with a tighter budget. It can be challenging to implement without technical knowledge, as customization may need developer support, making it more difficult for non-technical users to customize the software to suit their unique business requirements.
- **Microsoft Excel.** According to Nugrahani (2025), it is a widely used and most familiar accounting software with accounting capabilities that are useful for easily analyzing tax compliance information online and offline. Microsoft Excel offers accounting capabilities that are useful for easily analyzing and managing financial data making it more practical accounting software. However, Excel is not a dedicated accounting software. It requires manual updates and monitoring for intricate financial workflows, which can increase the margin for errors and necessitate more time from users.
- **Datamolino.** Datamolino is an accounting software that automates processing of accounting documents like invoices, receipts, and bills. It is commonly used by accounting firms and SMEs alongside Xero or QuickBooks Online (Lazanis,

2024). SaaSHub (2023) mentioned that the price of Datamolino can be a problem for startups and small companies, although it is equipped with solid features. Though it has a trial period, it is too brief for users to investigate and test all the features thoroughly. Despite having an easy-to-use interface, there could be a learning process for new customers to maximize all its features. It also needs a stable internet connection since it is a cloud solution. Users also complain that customer support is slow to respond and fix problems. Lastly, although Datamolino is excellent for processing invoices and receipts, its advanced accounting features are limited.

- **Approval Max.** An accounting software that is easy to use and helps businesses manage finances better, like handling the approval of bills, invoices, and purchase orders, and integrates well with Xero. It also keeps track of the business transactions and everything, organizes financial data for better audit preparation, reduces errors, and secures financial reports (Approval Max, 2016). XU Magazine (2024) stated that the “Review and Coding” option in Approval Max addresses data access and bill editing limitation problems by enabling bill editing as a step within the approval process, i.e., done without touching Xero or the data entry interface. The procedure is designed so that approvers and reviewers view only those bills and bill-related data of interest for this task. Moreover, reviewers have a restricted scope of changes they can make, like splitting line items or altering the tracking category.
- **MileIQ.** Lazanis (2024) mentions that the design of MileIQ was meant to painlessly track business trips, which is particularly useful for those seeking to maximize tax deductions or streamline reimbursement processes. While it is not a comprehensive accounting software, MileIQ specializes in logging and

categorizing drives, making it a valuable tool for expense tracking related to vehicle use.

- **Airwallex.** Airwallex is a platform that can be integrated into an existing accounting software to simplify financial processes, enabling the automatic synchronization of transaction data, which helps to simplify overall financial management through expediting monthly reconciliations. (Lau, K. 2024). Au (2025) only offers business accounts for businesses, not individuals. They provide few banking amenities, including the lack of interest-bearing accounts or letters of credit. They also limit the transactions according to the risk profile of businesses, much the same way most banks do.
- **Firstbase.** SoftwareSuggest (2025) defined it as an online platform that simplifies starting and managing a business, offering a variety of powerful accounting tools and advanced functionalities such as invoicing, expense tracking, payroll integration, multi-currency support, tax management, inventory management, and more. It also offers mobile access and third-party integrations. According to JoinSecret (n.d.), some users have reported server errors leading to unexpected charges in a software review. Others have reported slow or unresponsive customer support, leading to issues with unexpected plan cancellations, interfering with their business operations, and confusing them. First Base has numerous partners, but they are not responsible for the advice from these partners, which can result in expensive errors, like opening a mailbox in the wrong place.
- **HostBooks GST.** Rauniyar (2024) defined HostBooks as cloud-based Indian accounting software that helps businesses manage their finances smartly and simply. It automates tasks like creating invoices, tracking expenses, filing taxes,

and matching bank transactions. HostBooks is accessible anytime and anywhere, making it very helpful for business owners, accountants, and teams who need to work on their accounts even when not in their office. It provides real-time financial updates, helping businesses work better by saving time, cutting costs, and keeping financial records clear and accurate. Software Suggest (2025) received a review that the software only offers limited customization options, which may not be suitable for the particular requirements of every organization, as well as limited integration with other programs.

- **mybooks.** mybooks (capitalized as such) is a cloud-based accounting program designed as an easy-to-use cloud accounting platform aimed at freelancers, startups, and small businesses, especially those without a dedicated accountant (Indeed, n.d.).
- **Socius.** Socius Accounting is a robust accounting system that allows taking control over finance through a straightforward process of invoicing, a transaction ledger that allows searching through every transaction made easier to use with the transaction list feature, and a Financial Statements page that can easily help in planning for the future of the company (Driggers, 2025).
- **NetSuite ERP.** According to Oracle NetSuite (n.d.), it is an accounting software that helps businesses manage their finances more easily through automating tasks like invoicing, bill payments, and reconciling accounts while providing real-time insights into the financial health of the company to help in decision making, as well as saving time and reducing errors. It benefits growing businesses offering features to manage multiple departments or locations; however, it may be more complex for smaller companies with simpler needs.

- **Airbase.** According to NetSuite (2025), Airbase is an accounting software mainly used to control and track company expenses through automated payment features. It organizes expenses into categories, connects all the data to the accounting system of the company, and gives real-time reports on the financial status of the business at any time. It helps companies save time, reduce mistakes, and stay organized by integrating with other tools like QuickBooks and NetSuite. It makes it much easier to keep everything coordinated, avoid errors from copying data between systems, work online, and be accessible anywhere. Join Secret (n.d.) stated that since Airbase is a new product, not all its features are available upfront, and customers must invest significant time in assessing their AP process requirements before they move forward. It also lacks international payment support, limiting companies that have a global presence. Airbase currently does not have an Expense Reimbursements feature, which finance teams highly anticipate. Also, although Airbase supports creating digital cards, it does not support comprehensive analytics like spend category metrics.
- **Gaviti.** Gaviti is an accounting tool that helps businesses manage their accounts receivable more efficiently. It streamlines invoicing and collections by automating routine tasks, making it easier for companies to follow up on payments. Using Gaviti, businesses can speed up cash flow, minimize the number of overdue invoices, and improve the overall payment collection process (Accounts Junction., n.d.).
- **ADP Workforce Now.** ADP Workforce management (WFM) software is a suite of tools that helps ensure that employees are in the right place, at the right time for maximum productivity (ADP, n.d.). It allows businesses to optimize employee scheduling; labor forecasting; time and attendance tracking; leave

management; and rule or policy enforcement platforms to assist with regulatory compliance. PeerSpot (2023) summarized the cons of ADP Workforce Now as the payroll aspects need enhancement and addressed a few issues floating within. One of them was that there must be an improvement in the report development and generation to keep up with competitors. Customer support lacks sufficient comprehension and effectiveness in answering questions. There should also be an enhancement in the usability of the benefits portal for a better user experience. Generally, the complexity of the system is a significant challenge to users.

Though accounting software has many benefits, some challenges arise in the field. Chandra (2022) stated that a few of the significant problems of cloud technology include: the security of cloud accounting data, which lacks standardized protocols to govern its protection; the policies of service institutions, which are not sufficiently robust; the requirement for consistent internet connectivity for cloud technology, which might not always be feasible; security concerns related to cloud usage, such as the potential exposure of confidential data due to service disruption; the increasing vulnerability of data stored in the cloud as its usage becomes more prevalent; and the fact that when individuals upload data to the cloud, they entrust it to a group of people whom they have never personally met. In an article released by NI Business Info (n.d.) the disadvantages of using accounting software are its price, or the package price, which is small compared with other expenses, this usually costs greater than a paper-based system; Installation, manual accounts tend to be more straightforward to install and can be more versatile than computerized accounting. Some initial assistance is likely to be required when installing accounting software, and the system provider or accountant will generally make a charge for this service; There might be a need to buy for maintenance—the annual maintenance and support for the package; Specialized

requirements, the accounts package will usually be appropriate for most forms of business; specialist businesses can, however, have to adapt the package or alter procedures to gain benefits from accounting software. Accounting software can occasionally also have a steep learning curve, and if someone prefers setting up ledgers and books by hand, manual accounting might be an easier route.

Advantages of Accounting Software

Baylon *et al.* (n.d.) examined the extent to which IT skills were acquired by undergraduate accounting students and their relevance in the workplace. The study found that while students had a firm grasp of basic Microsoft office applications, particularly Microsoft Word, there was a noted need to improve Excel formulas and presentation designs. More importantly, the usage of Accounting Information Systems (AIS), such as SAP and QuickBooks, was learned to only an average extent. Despite this, these systems are highly valued in professional settings due to their role in improving the accuracy and efficiency of financial processes.

The findings of Baylon *et al.* align with previous studies emphasizing the practical benefits of accounting software. Arcega *et al.* (2015) reported that 64.29% of SMEs in Lipa City used computerized accounting software, with QuickBooks being a notable example. Adopting such software provides key workplace advantages—automated data entry, real-time reporting, and enhanced accuracy—all of which contribute to increased productivity and minimized human error in financial transactions.

Furthermore, Baylon *et al.* emphasized that the private sector strongly emphasizes using AIS for transaction recording and reporting. In contrast, public sector firms prioritize IT audit skills and computer-assisted audit techniques (CAATs). These

tools assist in ensuring data integrity and regulatory compliance and support efficient decision-making based on timely financial information.

These insights suggest that BSA graduates who have acquired proficiency in accounting software gain tangible advantages in the workplace. Such benefits include improved efficiency, accuracy in financial reporting, and the ability to meet employer expectations regarding technological competence. This reflects the increasing demand for accountants who can adapt to automated systems and evolving digital platforms.

Pan and Seow (2016) highlighted that graduates proficient in accounting software enjoy significant advantages in their professional roles. These individuals are better equipped to manage financial records, analyze data, and generate reports with improved efficiency. The automation capabilities of accounting software reduce the chances of mistakes, ensuring more accurate financial data and faster task execution. The proficiency in accounting software boosts the confidence and autonomy of BSA graduates, enabling them to carry out their tasks independently. This increased self-reliance reduces the need for supervision and contributes to a more productive and positive work environment. Moreover, the growing demand for proficiency in accounting software in the job market has made these graduates more competitive, enhancing their employability and opening doors to a broader range of career opportunities.

Pan *et al.* (2025) pointed out that to keep up with the digital revolution, the accounting courses provided in universities are being redesigned to enable students who achieve a bachelor's degree to become digitally capable at graduation (Polimeni & Burke, 2021; Qasim & Kharbat, 2020). Within a survey of the US university accounting academic department (Richardson & Shan, 2019), it was discovered that 90.7 percent

of accounting department chairs think data analytics should be added to the curriculum of accounting, and 59.3 percent of them have plans to offer a data analytics course within their programs. Likewise, Ballou *et al.* (2018) affirm that data analytics must be embedded in the undergraduate accounting curriculum. Qasim and Kharbat also point to a growing interest in the accounting profession towards data analytics adoption. Although there is little debate that data analytics knowledge and skills are valuable to an accounting education, the difficulty for most accounting academic departments is integrating these data analytics topics into an already crowded undergraduate curriculum.

Khoshabri *et al.* (2025) emphasized the significance of cloud accounting for enhancing the quality of financial reports. Through cloud solutions, organizations can achieve greater efficiency, accuracy, and transparency in financial reporting. Incorporating automated processes, real-time reporting, and advanced security measures makes decision-making and compliance requirements superior. Their study also highlighted that cloud accounting is an improvement in technology and a strategic resource that can transform financial management practices. Organizations using cloud accounting can experience reduced operating costs, greater access to data, and enhanced compliance with financial reporting standards. Despite numerous benefits, they also discovered particular challenges in implementing cloud accounting, such as data security, complexity of integration, and the need for adequate training and change management. These challenges must be addressed so that organizations can fully exploit the potential of cloud accounting.

Rex (2024) stated that the right accounting software benefits finance professionals in organizations of all sizes. Accounting software can handle tracking expenses and income, generate reports, and calculate interest in real-time and error-free.

ERP platforms with cross-functional modules can reduce the steps needed to complete accounting tasks, eliminating inefficiencies such as toggling between tools and manual work, boosting productivity. Time saved can be reinvested in strategic tasks that impact business profitability.

The toggle tax that results from the opening and closing of software tools, toggling between spreadsheets, hunting down receipts to company credit cards or juggling multiple payment reminder email drafts, which accounts for around four hours of unproductive work a week, or almost ten percent of all time spent at work for the year can be eliminated or reduced and thus increasing efficiency by boosting the productivity of people and saving time overall. This extra time can be reinvested in strategic and judgment-based accounting tasks that impact the profitability of a business.

In addition, accounting software can calculate, send, and track invoices, recognize payments, and trigger reminders, saving time and reducing disputes. It also improves the client experience through payment portals. This helps businesses get paid quickly and accurately, strengthening relationships and supporting recurring revenue. It also helps identify wasteful spending, calculate taxes, and optimize deductions to improve cash flow.

Cloud-based accounting software platforms are also valuable for securing sensitive financial data. Accounting software aids accountants in their work of recording and reporting the financial transactions of firms. However, firms may have different needs—firms use simple accounting software, while others use complex accounting software. It is useful in recovering old accounting data, which makes it easier and helpful for internal and external audits. According to Kenton (2021), accounting software simplifies calculations, making them easier to understand and

quicker to analyze, simplifying calculations and speeding up financial analysis. Using accounting software supports efficiency in creating reports that could be done in a couple of clicks instead of wasting hours compiling information for a spreadsheet. In a study by Robinson (2024), accounting software enhances operational efficiency by automating time-consuming tasks such as bookkeeping, invoicing, and payroll processing. Additionally, productivity in organizations using accounting software reported an increase of 20%, and value-driven activities of employees are given emphasis. Data is vulnerable at every access point between uploads, downloads, emails, and print copies. Cloud-based accounting software platforms are some of the best productivity tools for accountants because they recognize the importance of locking down sensitive financial data.

Moreover, accuracy improvement is one of the most significant and noticeable impacts of accounting software. Traditional accounting likely results in inaccurate information and reports that could affect decision-making. The possibility of errors and their risks are minimized thanks to accounting software, thus increasing the accuracy of employees, which lessens employee stress through importing transactions and providing real-time data validation. Accounting errors are a product of stress to employees and could lead to compliance issues, inaccurate conclusions, and financial discrepancies. Accounting software not only corrects misleading information but also contributes to better transparency.

According to Tagamolila (2023), accounting software assists companies of whatever size to effectively perform accounting tasks and make the accounting process smoother by streamlining financial operations like sales tracking, payroll, and invoice processing. This reduces the risk of errors and improves the quality of the outputs created by the team. The development of technology has given rise to a variety of

accounting software. It should be chosen according to the business operations of the company.

According to Imene and Imhanzenobe (2020), today's accountants mostly rely upon hardware and software technologies in order to perform accounting activities and facilitate appropriate reporting, which has led to developing advanced technologies utilized for capturing, processing, and storing financial data. Practicing accountants are now transforming the way they communicate and work with stakeholders they work for and with, establishing new working habits that are technology-driven, and redefining their expertise to adapt to new requirements (ACCA, 2013).

Swieboda (2016) explains that the available accounting systems on the market vary from straightforward ones built on Excel spreadsheets to more advanced systems for small and medium-sized enterprises, to the most advanced, such as SAP, BAAN, or IFS. Today, financial records stored digitally on computer hard drives allow accountants to file tax returns directly from their desks. These systems also make it easier to manage the import and export of documents. Electronic accounting tools offer quick access to archived data, make it easy to correct past entries, and often include helpful reminders and tips for handling common errors in accounting records. Because today hard disks of computers are used to store, register, and evidence financial records, tax returns can be filed at tax offices directly without leaving the desk of an accountant, and importing and exporting documents can be managed easily. The electronic systems provide quick and straightforward access to archived data, simple correction of executed data, and offer many reminders and tips on handling errors in accounting records.

Arep *et al.* (2025) stated that the accounting software used has been functioning effectively, as evidenced by the system alignment with the company's financial

activities in preparing the company's financial statements. The 6 dimensions of Delone and McLean's Information System Success Model were utilized to assess accurate accounting software implementation effectiveness by which it ensures effective system and information quality, ease of use, financial staff satisfaction, guaranteed service quality, and positive impact upon the individual and company performance. Barriers in using accounting software arise when the internet connectivity starts to decline, which results in delays in the processing of financial statements. The impediment does not have a severe effect on the effectiveness of the utilization of accurate accounting software, as the problem can be solved by replacing the internet service used by the company. Suggestions are made by Arep *et al.* to the future researchers to install a reliable internet network and give comprehensive training on operating accurate accounting software.

The study of Nwanko *et al.* (2025) provides useful information regarding the effects of automated accounting packages on the financial operations of Nigerian SMEs. Most of the respondents indicated significant improvements in financial reporting accuracy and reliability. Particularly, most of the SMEs acknowledged that automated accounting systems made their financial information more precise compared to manual reporting, resulting in more trustworthy financial reports. Additionally, the utilization of automated software greatly enhanced the velocity of report production, thus increasing the overall performance of financial activities. This points to the critical function that automated accounting software has in maximizing the financial management processes of SMEs. However, despite all these benefits, some challenges prevent the complete uptake and proper use of automated accounting software. The steep prices of acquiring and retaining the software proved to be the most frequently mentioned problem, followed by inadequate technical ability among employees.

Resistance from employees with a penchant for old-school accounting also proved to be a roadblock. Although most respondents thought that the process of implementation was tractable, there was a significant number who faced challenges, notably because of the inherent technicalities involved. These results suggested that although automated accounting software can greatly improve financial operations, SMEs encounter a number of challenges that could hinder their potential to fully reap its benefits. To address these challenges, future initiatives should concentrate on making the software more accessible, providing in-depth training to employees, and instilling a culture that is open to technological change in SMEs.

Manansala *et al.* (2024) stated that the BPO industry requires accounting graduates to have software proficiency, communication, active learning, and critical thinking.

Integration of Accounting Software into University Curricula

With technology being prevalent in the world today, the world must keep pace in order not to get drowned in this novel creation. For instance, in order for one to know how to do it, one must learn how to do it. In the same sense, one must learn technology in order to harness its full potential. For that reason, integrating accounting software into university curricula is crucial to maximize the capacity technology gives the world. Hence, this part of the review will focus on the advantages of integrating technology into other institutions and organizations.

Accountants must be adaptable and continuously learn in the fast-changing digital environment of today. Those who studied accounting software during their undergraduate studies enhanced their career prospects, improved efficiency and accuracy in financial reporting, and increased employability in the modern workforce.

The growing use of digital accounting practices drives up the demand for accounting professionals with technology expertise, and proficiency in technology is a highly valued asset these days. They must be proficient in data analytics, cloud-based accounting software, blockchain, and distributed ledger technologies to establish a solid career in the area (LSU Alexandria Newsroom, 2023; Tagamolila, 2023; Tahil, 2024; Lee *et al.*, 2018; Dapiton & Gano-an, 2023).

Because of the demands of the profession, Meyer (2021) supports the above statement; incorporating technology into the accounting curriculum has become more crucial. Tertiary institutions, one example, are now required to integrate more practical and technological content into their curriculum, including utilizing software such as QuickBooks, Microsoft Excel, and data analytics.

Companies looking for graduates already competent in technological expertise, specifically automation, data management, and protection, are driving this transformation. Some universities are partnering with technological companies and utilizing certifications to prepare students for the specifications of the industry upon graduation (*see Lee et al.*, 2018). For instance, the University of North Carolina at Greensboro (Meyer, 2021) implemented adjustments in their curriculum to incorporate technology at all levels of their accounting program instead of just through standalone courses, including using such tools as Tableau, Power BI, and Python, as well as instructing students in critical thinking about data. The exposure of the students to those tools better equipped them for placements and internships, which could indicate a greater success in taking learning from an academic environment into practice.

Nickell and Chambers (2022) highlighted that accounting education courses need to change and improve to incorporate technological skills in accordance with the

updated CPA examinations and the new CPA licensure model. The CPA Evolution Initiative, being the joint effort of American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) and National Association of State Boards of Accountancy (NASBA), utilized a “core-plus-discipline” licensure model from 2024 onwards, wherein all candidates are required to be technology- and data analytics-competent, irrespective of field of specialization. These include *Business Analysis and Reporting*, *Information Systems and Controls*, and *Tax Compliance and Planning*. The model curriculum of AICPA reinforces these by including digital acumen and data analytics across all areas of the CPA examinations. To such changing requirements, Nickell and Chambers provided ways of incorporating technology into accounting courses, suggesting the application of Microsoft Excel in classroom exercises to learn elementary-level skills. In audit classes, they proposed the application of CAAT and data analytics software such as IDEA and Alteryx, both of which have free student versions and instruction sets.

The Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) required all accredited accounting programs to include information technology as part of their curriculum back in 2013, later expanding in 2018 to include requirements that students and faculty should master existing and new technologies. Applying these changes is not easy, with challenges such as the absence of convergence among instructors and the availability of trained staff to educate on these new technologies, particularly in areas like data analytics and information security. They also discussed how future CPA licensure will emphasize the application of technology within accounting and how meeting these needs requires reforming the accounting curricula, citing institutional support and implementation challenges. Overall, their findings confirm that, if students are to perform effectively in the modern-day accounting world, digital tools and

analytics knowledge must be a prominent aspect of their tertiary studies(Nickell & Chambers, 2022).

Concerning the use of tools, Lee *et al.* (2018) found that Microsoft Excel is the most widely used software tool, considered essential for new hires, and needed priority in university accounting courses. The importance of Microsoft Excel was similar across various accounting fields, such as audit, tax, advisory, and corporate, and across all levels of experience. In addition to Microsoft Excel, Adobe Acrobat, Microsoft PowerPoint, accounting/ERP software, and the FASB Codification were the most often used tools across various accounting fields and experience levels. Moreover, practitioners suggested that data analytics and visualization skills matter and that data analytics skills are more significant than data visualization skills. The research adds to the literature on accounting information systems by identifying particular software and tools relevant to the accounting profession and offering advice concerning the software and tools that university accountancy programs should highlight.

The finance and accounting field heavily depends on several accounting software programs to efficiently and accurately handle finances (Tagamolila, 2023). Xero, QuickBooks Desktop, QuickBooks, and FreshBooks are among the most popular accounting software of today. Xero is a cloud accounting solution that supports small to medium-sized businesses, with features like automatic transaction updates through bank feeds, support for multiple currencies, payroll processing, inventory management, seamless integrations with third-party applications, and detailed financial reporting. The desktop version supports advanced reporting and analysis, inventory management, job and project tracking, and industry-specific offerings to support businesses run from one site. Its cloud companion has similar features, with the advantage of being cloud-based and allowing collaboration and synchronization with third-party tools. FreshBooks

comes with a friendly interface suitable for small businesses or individuals without experience in accounting and features time tracking, invoicing, expense monitoring, and tax preparation capabilities.

Digital literacy is crucial for the global competitiveness of the students. Tahil (2024) emphasizes role of computers in simplifying daily tasks, facilitating rapid communication, and efficiently solving complex problems. Studying computers promotes intellectual growth. Hackbarth, Dow, and Janvrin (2010) found that producing competent accountants requires the combination of technology-equipped training environments and traditional classroom instruction to enhance learning experience of the students most effectively. Abou-Ei-Sood (2024) provides evidence on the usefulness of accounting software in the classroom.

Additionally, the usefulness of QuickBooks, a popular accounting program created by Intuit primarily for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), was investigated. It was found out in this study that integrating QuickBooks in the curriculum enhanced their overall learning experience and boosted their interest and engagement in a “boring” subject. Moreover, Tahil considers QuickBooks more effective when practiced or used in the lab during class than when taught theoretically, and its usefulness increases during times of uncertainty.

Similarly, Mdingi (2024) states that in the world today, education without integrating computer applications leaves students unprepared for the realities of modern workplaces. In South Africa, higher education institutions have long integrated computerized accounting systems into their accounting qualifications curriculum. However, that is not the case with the high school accounting curriculum. The findings of this study provide evidence that learners are keen on technologically driven lessons,

confirming that Generation Z students are very interested in technologically driven lessons. Furthermore, teachers believe class attendance will improve when learners enjoy their lessons. Class attendance is critical in accounting, as each lesson builds from the previous one. A positive attitude yields a conducive and productive learning and teaching environment. Accounting requires an in-depth understanding of its principles to apply them appropriately. The findings indicate that computerized accounting provides a practical reality of how accounting rules and principles are processed. According to accounting teachers, computerized accounting will take learners a step further from knowing accounting information to understanding how real businesses apply accounting information systems. Therefore, computerized accounting allows users to use the principles they learned. Complementing theoretical knowledge of accounting with computerized accounting enhances understanding of accounting principles and concepts and provides a lifelong learning experience to learners.

On the other hand, Dapiton and Gano-an (2023) centered their study on the rise of virtual accounting during COVID-19 and the implementation of lockdowns and social distancing. Many employees began shifting from the corporate setting to providing online accounting services. This transition has led to reliance on technology, as educational institutions have had to adapt their teaching methods and assessment approaches to mitigate the disruptions caused by lockdowns and physical distancing measures. These changes have reshaped the teaching process, emphasizing technology-assisted active learning. Students' engagement and interest in the course have been influenced accordingly (Sangster *et al.*, 2020). Papageorgiou (2014) investigated how incorporating computerized accounting into the curriculum could help students gain practical skills for the business world. They found that the students significantly improved their understanding of computerized accounting. Interestingly, the study also

revealed that a key benefit was the development of teamwork skills. The students learned how to work effectively in groups, which was a very valuable experience. The research suggests that integrating computerized accounting into the curriculum positively impacts students' skills and ability to collaborate.

Challenges in Integrating Technology in Classes

Gautam (2024) emphasized in the article that the role of technology in modern accounting has significantly changed. The adoption of new integrated technology introduces improvements in the accuracy and efficiency of operations; however, there are challenges for organizations and accountants that should be addressed.

These include resistance to change, where employees who have experience of using traditional accounting practices remain reluctant to use the new systems without knowledge of them. To overcome this, Gautam suggested thorough training where they can improve their skills and engage staff in the transition process in the world of accounting. The article also said that the implementation cost, i.e., software and hardware upgrade expenses and consultancy charge, needs to be appropriately evaluated, where the long-term return on investment needs to be evaluated. Another challenge in integrating technology is integration with current systems; incompatibility could cause disruption in workflow and data inconsistency unless careful planning and testing are executed.

Furthermore, Gautam mentioned that data privacy and security issues increase with emerging technologies, necessitating encryption, access controls, and periodic security audits to safeguard sensitive financial data. The article also noted the training and skill development, whereby employees require training to utilize the systems efficiently, requiring continuous learning support.

In addition, the article highlighted transition downtime, where changing systems temporarily impacts productivity and financial reporting unless alleviated by phased installations and backups. Finally, Gautam addressed rapid technological changes, explaining how accounting software becomes outdated, leaving companies to have to upgrade or replace systems much more often than in prior years to stay competitive.

Boulianne (2014) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of accounting software use on the acquisition of students' knowledge in accounting education. The study comprised 1,053 Canadian business school undergraduate accounting students who were allocated into three groups: students who worked through an accounting case manually, students who utilized accounting software, and students who initially worked through the case manually before utilizing the software. The results stated that students utilizing both manual and software methods showed the highest amount of knowledge attained. This can be interpreted to mean that an integrated approach aids in better comprehension of the accounting cycle compared to applying either alone. Nonetheless, the research further pointed out several challenges faced while incorporating accounting software into the learning process. The educators are concerned that the dependence on software might hinder the students' understanding of basic accounting concepts, since the software does much of the work, which could result in surface learning. In addition, students could become too reliant on the software, thus failing to acquire the critical analytical skills required for financial data interpretation. It was also mentioned that while the use of software can increase technical competence, it might not adequately address the theoretical and conceptual aspects of accounting education. A balanced instructional approach blending both conventional and technological approaches was therefore suggested.

Perlas, Reyes, and Victoria (2020), in their study at Cavite State University–Main Campus, support these findings by referring to similar challenges in the integration of Accounting Information Systems (AIS) in the BS Accountancy program. One of the major challenges they cited is the continuation of conventional teaching practices that focus on theoretical lectures and textbook-based teaching, which do not tend to incorporate modern information systems. This gap forms into minimal exposure and training for students, and they struggle to properly transfer to AIS in real accounting environments. The study also pointed out that the lack of user-friendly AIS tools and inadequate support for teachers to teach such systems creates an additional barrier to adoption. These findings emphasize the need for curriculum reform that not only includes the inclusion of hands-on AIS training but also prepares teachers with the tools and resources necessary to effectively teach these systems in ways that align more directly to industry requirements.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study focuses on understanding the use of accounting software among Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University and how this knowledge can guide curriculum development to meet workplace demands. Figure 1 visualizes the paradigm as follows:

Figure 1
Research Paradigm

The input includes demographic data such as year graduated and field of practice, software usage data, and factors influencing software choice. The process involves gathering data through surveys with BSA graduates to determine commonly used accounting software, analyzing the specific advantages graduates experience with these tools, and interpreting the findings to identify trends and gaps. The output consists of disseminating information through brochures and pamphlets about the accounting software used in the workplace, and providing insights for integrating accounting software in the current curriculum.

This framework serves as a structured guide to bridge the gap between academic preparation and the evolving technological demands of the accounting profession, ensuring that future accountants are equipped with the necessary software skills to thrive in their careers.

Synthesis

This review examines the relationship between accounting software utilization and the effectiveness of Palawan State University's (PSU) Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) curriculum through lenses of various studies and literatures, both locally and internationally. It investigates the impact of accounting software on accounting practices and argues for curriculum reform to equip graduates with necessary technological competencies. The study analyzes graduate demographics in terms of year graduated and professional field, accounting software usage, and the advantages, challenges, and opportunities inherent in curriculum integration to propose a strategic integration of AIS into the BSA program. The evolving landscape of accounting software from 2016 to 2020, characterized by the rise of QuickBooks, Xero, FreshBooks, Zoho Books, Wave Accounting, and Sage, provides a crucial context. This

dynamic environment necessitates a curriculum that equips graduates with practical skills in using widely used software. A positive correlation between work experience and professional development in Finland, the direct applicability to the Philippine context requires careful consideration, particularly concerning the potential for earlier graduates to have gained more practical experience with accounting software before its widespread adoption. The correlation between education levels and work performance highlights the potential for recent graduates to possess superior software skills due to updated curricula. This study hypothesizes that recent BSA graduates will demonstrate stronger theoretical knowledge, while earlier graduates may possess greater practical experience with accounting software. By analyzing software usage among graduates in relation to their graduation year, the research assesses curriculum effectiveness and alignment with industry demands. The advantages of accounting software proficiency—improved efficiency, accuracy, and employability—are well-documented. The shift from manual to automated systems enhances speed and accuracy, reduces errors, and improves client service and regulatory compliance. Cloud-based systems further enhance flexibility and collaboration.

The near-universal call for technology integration in accounting education is reinforced by the AICPA and NASBA's CPA Evolution Initiative, which emphasizes technology competency. Successful implementations of software like QuickBooks in educational settings demonstrate positive impacts on student engagement and future employability. However, challenges remain, including resistance to change, budgetary constraints, the need for teacher training, and the rapid pace of technological advancements. Therefore, a strategic and phased approach to integrating AIS into the PSU BSA curriculum is recommended. This approach should address the identified challenges through targeted teacher training programs, investment in appropriate

software and infrastructure, and the development of a curriculum that balances theoretical understanding with practical application. By proactively addressing these challenges and capitalizing on the documented benefits, the PSU BSA program can better prepare its graduates for success in the modern accounting profession.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlined the research methods used to examine the utilization of accounting software by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University and its impact on their workplace effectiveness. By identifying the specific software programs commonly used and analyzing the graduates' experiences, this study aimed to establish a basis for curriculum integration, bridging the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the modern accounting workplace.

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, which consisted of both qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative research design was utilized to explore the experiences and perspectives of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University regarding the use of accounting software in their workplaces. This approach is well-suited for understanding the lived experiences of individuals within the scope. The quantitative research design, meanwhile, was utilized for the presentation of results, containing numerical data collected from the interpreted survey questionnaires.

The researcher employed descriptive research to provide a comprehensive analysis of the accounting software commonly utilized by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy graduates of Palawan State University in their respective workplaces. This study aimed to identify the specific accounting software programs the participants use and the reasons behind their preference for these tools. Identifying the advantages and

benefits these software applications provide helps the graduates perform their tasks effectively and efficiently at work.

Research Locale

This research was conducted within the context of Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus, located at Tiniguiban Heights, Puerto Princesa City, Philippines. The researchers specifically focused on individuals who had completed a Bachelor of Science in Accountancy degree between 2016 and 2020 from Palawan State University. The study also extends to the workplaces of these graduates, using online platforms to gather data and insights about their application of accounting software. Due to the prevalence of graduates from Palawan State University working outside the province and even outside the Philippines, the researcher utilized online survey questionnaires to gather information from these individuals remotely, ensuring a broader representation of their experiences.

Population of the Study

The target respondents were Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University who entered the accounting profession between the years 2016 and 2020. This allowed the researchers to gather insights into the experiences of recent graduates regarding the use of accounting software in their workplaces. By understanding how these recent graduates utilize software skills in their workplaces, we can identify the most relevant software programs for integration into the BSA curriculum, bridging the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the modern accounting workplace. This study served as a foundation for integrating essential software skills into the BSA curriculum, ensuring that future graduates are equipped with the necessary skills to thrive in the evolving accounting landscape.

Data Collection Procedure

To gather in-depth insights into the use of accounting software by BSA graduates from PSU, the following data collection and sampling procedures were employed:

- 1. Respondent Selection:** The researchers collected an official list of students who graduated Bachelor of Science in Accountancy from Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus during the years 2016 to 2020. The information was made available by the office of the University Registrar. The researchers submitted a letter (refer to the related correspondence dated 3 February 2025 at Appendix B: Letters and Other Communications). According to the registrar, there are officially one hundred seven (107) graduates from the years 2016 to 2020. From there, the researchers contacted all the respondents for the study. This is what is called a purposive sampling, as the researchers delimited their respondents those the graduated at the above date, meant to purposely focus on those related to the study at hand. Regardless whether or not the respondents accept or refuse the survey is beyond the control of the researchers, which shall be discussed in depth in the proceeding step.
- 2. Data Gathering:** The researchers conducted an initial pilot testing in the Accounting Office of Palawan State University last 3 to 8 February 2025 (see corresponding letter attached at Appendix B: Letters and Other Communications) involving eight CPAs for the validation of structured questionnaires which was subsequently granted approval with minor revisions, which includes expounding on questions related to Section 2

(refer to section Questionnaire Design in this chapter). Following the revisions and suggestions requested by the experts, the researchers then distributed the revised questionnaire online through the respondent's available communication channels and forwarded them the link to the electronic version of the form to get their responses. Overall, out of 107 graduates from 2016 to 2020, only 33 responded to the researchers, with one withdrawal due to reasons undisclosed to the researchers. Aside from this, the researchers conducted an interview to gather information from the respondents that gave a more detailed elaboration of the respondent's experience and its importance from their work. The researchers emphasized the confidentiality of the data collected and highlighted that participation is purely voluntary. Provisions were made for respondents who choose to withdraw from the study, and their decision was respected. Researchers did not replace withdrawn respondents, as purposive sampling relies on specific criteria for participant selection. Any gaps resulting from withdrawals were transparently disclosed in the study's findings to highlight potential limitations and ensure the integrity of the research process.

Research Flowchart

This study follows a set of procedure that was made in order to visualize its ideation to its finalization, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
Research Flowchart

The study started with the initial observation of the researchers in the Department of Accountancy and Management Accounting, and they have found out that there exist little to no information regarding accounting software in the current curriculum, which is crucial as there was already information about the revisions of the licensure examinations of the Certified Public Accountants that will be made. This led them to review related literature about the matter, where they have found out about the commonly-used accounting software across the globe. From there, they formulated the core problem of the study, thereafter making its objectives that seek to answer those problem. From the objectives, they composed the title of this study and its design.

The design of the study was divided into two major parts: the instrument and the statistical analysis. The statistical analysis will be done with the use of statistical applications like *jamovi* and *Microsoft Excel*, aiming to support the researchers in arriving at meaningful data to interpret. The research instrument, meanwhile, focused

on seeking which mode of gathering will be made in order to compile data for interpretation, where the researchers chose to employ a survey for this matter.

Questionnaire formulation and respondent selection were made, ensuring that the survey shall live to its purpose of gathering data for interpretation, hence their interconnection. Pilot testing was made as a confirmation of the effectiveness of the research instrument, and any improvements were duly done back to its formulation before it was disseminated to the intended respondents through an electronic form.

With the gathered data, the research team undertakes data analysis, applying statistical methodologies and using statistical software for accuracy. Data interpretation leads to meaningful insights, where trends, correlations, and findings emerge. These inform the conclusions and recommendations, ensuring the research contributes to existing knowledge and practical applications.

Before finalizing the study through in peer review discussions, the researchers refined interpretations, and strengthened conclusions. With revisions incorporated, the study reaches completion, ready for inclusion in the broader academic field, ensuring its findings contribute to ongoing advancements in the discipline. This structured approach ensures the research remains methodical, credible, and impactful in addressing key questions and informing practical solutions.

Questionnaire Design

In conducting the study on the experience of the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University regarding accounting software, the primary research instrument is a structured questionnaire. A structured questionnaire was developed to gather data about the software programs used by BSA

graduates, the most commonly used accounting software, the perceived advantages, and their recommendations for curriculum integration. The questionnaire included:

Section 1. This section aimed to gather essential demographic information from participants, including their year of graduation and their current field of practice. Closed-ended questions were utilized for this purpose, ensuring a standardized and easily quantifiable data collection process.

Section 2. This section examines the accounting software programs used by graduates in their professional practice. Multiple-choice questions and a frequency scale were utilized to identify and determine the most commonly used software. To enhance the depth and reliability of the findings, additional questions were included, such as assessing the level of difficulty experienced with the software and identifying where respondents first acquired their skills. These measures provided a more comprehensive understanding of the graduates' exposure to and proficiency in accounting software.

Section 3. This section helped to understand the perceived benefits of accounting software, using a five-point Likert scale. This scale assessed the perceived importance of specific advantages associated with accounting software use, providing valuable insights into the factors driving software adoption and preference.

Section 4. This section aimed to gather valuable recommendations from graduates regarding specific software programs they believe should be included in the BSA curriculum. Close-ended questions encouraged participants to elaborate on their choices and provide detailed reasons for

their selections, providing a rich qualitative data source for informed curriculum development.

Ethical Consideration

Before the study was conducted, for ethical research considerations, the respondents have received a detailed briefing and crucial information regarding the purpose of this study. To fulfill the avoidance of potential harm and to ensure anonymity and secrecy, all information were held and handled with utmost confidentiality by not disclosing the names and identities of the participants of this study, in accordance with RA 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, including all other guidelines and issuances, as well as its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) by the National Privacy Commission (NPC).

Statistical Analysis

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to data analysis, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to gain a comprehensive understanding of the accounting software commonly used by BSA graduates.

Descriptive statistics is used for the analysis of quantitative data to (1) examine the demographic characteristics of the sample, (2) determine the most frequently used accounting software, and (3) analyze the importance of different advantages of software use using Likert scale data. The data such as the weighted average from those Likert scale data will be interpreted through the use of statistical analysis software such as *jamovi* and *Microsoft Excel*.

Thematic analysis was used in the analysis of qualitative data to examine the data from focus groups. This involved understanding how graduates use software in

their day-to-day work, the specific tasks they perform, and the challenges they face. This will explore in-depth insights into the benefits the graduates experienced from using software, beyond the quantitative data, and identify key software programs and skills that graduates recommend for inclusion in the curriculum.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the analysis of data gathered from the survey questionnaire. The findings are aligned with the research questions that guided the study. Data were analyzed to examine BSA graduates from Palawan State University, focusing on their graduation year, career field, and the most commonly used accounting software. It also assessed the advantages of using accounting software in the workplace and developed recommendations for its integration into the BSA curriculum.

Demographic Profile

This section profiles the respondents as to two variables—year graduated, and sector concerned. This is to trace down how they answer in their respectively field of work. Figure 2 focuses which year the respondents have graduated in the BSA program at Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus.

Figure 3
Year Graduated

The figure above shows the overall composition of respondents in accordance with the year graduated. 36.4% of the respondents graduated in 2019; 30.3% in 2018;

21.2% in 2017; 9.1% in 2016, and 3% in 2020. The majority of respondents are from the years 2016 to 2019.

This suggests that graduates from the year 2020, with only two (2) respondents, represent the smallest percentage due to their limited population. In contrast, graduates from 2016, despite being the second-largest group with twenty-nine (29) respondents may indicate that the majority of individuals who graduated that year are unreachable due to the demands of their workplace, hindering their time to participate in the survey.

The second question of the demographic profile focuses on the which sector those the respondents work to. Results were as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4
Field Practicing the Profession

The figure above shows the composition of respondents based on the sectors where they are currently practicing their profession. The Government sector is the largest, covering 42.42% of the population, followed by the Private sector with 39.39%, and lastly the Public sector with 18.18%. The “Academe” category is listed but has no representation shown in the graph because none of the respondents indicated that they

are practicing in the said sector. Thus, the academe sector will not be included in the subsequent presentations. Table 1, titled Demographic Matrix, provides a structured representation of the respondents based on the sectors in which they currently practice their profession and the year which they graduated.

Table 1
Demographic Matrix

<i>Year</i>	<i>Sector</i>				<i>Total</i>
	<i>Government</i>	<i>Private</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>Academe</i>	
2020	0	0	1	0	1
2019	7	4	1	0	12
2018	4	4	2	0	10
2017	2	4	1	0	7
2016	1	1	1	0	3
TOTAL	14	13	6	0	33

The table illustrates the distribution of respondents across two categories: year graduated and sector practicing the profession. As shown, the highest number of respondents graduated in 2019, comprising twelve (12) individuals. Of these, seven (7) are employed in the government sector, four (4) in the Private sector, and one (1) in the Public sector. The year 2018 follows with ten (10) graduates, distributed as four (4) in government, four (4) in Private, and two (2) in Public employment. In 2017, seven (7) graduates were reported, with two (2) entering government service, four (4) joining the Private sector, and one (1) joining the Public sector. In 2016, three (3) respondents graduated, with one (1) working in each of the government, Private, and Public sectors.

Meanwhile, one (1) respondent graduated in 2020 and is currently employed in the Public sector.

Commonly Used Accounting Software by the BSA Graduates in their Workplace

The second section of the result focused on what accounting was used in the workplace by the respondents. Table 2 is a list of accounting software commonly used in the workplace and the demographics of those using this software among the BSA graduates of Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus.

Table 2
Accounting Software Used in the Workplace

<i>Software</i>	<i>Sector</i>			<i>f</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
	<i>Government</i>	<i>Private</i>	<i>Public</i>		
Microsoft Excel	12	12	5	29	87.88%
Quickbooks	6	8	3	17	51.52%
Oracle NetSuite	3	5	0	8	24.24%
Xero	1	3	2	6	18.18%
SAP	0	4	1	5	15.15%
Sage	1	2	0	3	9.09%
NetSuite ERP	0	2	0	2	6.06%
Zoho Books	0	0	1	1	3.03%
Wave	0	1	0	1	3.03%
MYOB	0	1	0	1	3.03%
easyFS	1	0	0	1	3.03%
JuanTax	0	0	1	1	3.03%
Others	4	4	1	9	27.27%

The table above presents the software utilized by respondents in their workplace. As indicated, Microsoft Excel emerged as the most frequently used, with 87.88% of respondents (29 out of 33) incorporating it into their tasks. QuickBooks followed, being

employed by 51.52% of respondents (17 out of 33). Meanwhile, Oracle NetSuite, Xero, and SAP demonstrated notable usage, with adoption rates of 24.24%, 18.18%, and 15.15%, respectively. Sage and NetSuite ERP exhibited comparatively lower yet appreciable levels of utilization, accounting for 9.09% and 6.06% of respondents, respectively. The remaining software applications showed significantly lower usage frequencies, many with zero reported use.

In terms of sector-specific usage, Microsoft Excel had a total of twenty-nine (29) respondents: twelve (12) from the government sector, twelve (12) from the private sector, and five (5) from the public sector. This shows that Microsoft Excel is especially useful in the government and private sectors. QuickBooks had a total of seventeen (17) users: six (6) from the government sector, eight (8) from the private sector, and three (3) from the public sector. This indicates that QuickBooks was widely adopted across all sectors, with the private sector showing the highest usage. Oracle NetSuite had eight (8) users: three (3) from the government sector and five (5) from the private sector. The public sector had no recorded use of Oracle NetSuite, suggesting it was more commonly implemented in government and private organizations.

Findings show the usage of accounting software in different sectors. The Microsoft Excel is particularly applicable in the private and government sectors. This indicates that Microsoft Excel is the most commonly used accounting software in these sectors because it is easy to access and flexible. It is an easily recognized application with accounting functionality beneficial in studying financial data, as indicated by JuanTax (n.d.). But it is not an exclusive accounting software and demands effort for specific functions. QuickBooks was also used in the private and government sectors. This indicates that from 2016 to 2020, QuickBooks was utilized accounting software in

the workplace. It is supported by Milestone Team (2024), which states that QuickBooks is the most well-known and utilized accounting software, particularly among SMEs, due to its high functionality and ease of compatibility with other tools. Oracle NetSuite also had a significant response, it mostly used in the government and private sectors. As Nugrahani (2025) describes, Oracle NetSuite provides full financial and business management capabilities. Its usage could be affected by premium pricing and fewer built-in features for some functions. FreshBooks was not commonly seen being used, as it is primarily for freelancers, small businesses, and entrepreneurs who do not need extensive accounting skills. Most of the respondents operate in industries with financial requirements, which FreshBooks might not completely used to (Whiz Consulting, 2023).

Other programs like Kashoo Cloud Accounting, Odoo Accounting, QNE Software, HashMicro, Account Edge Pro, and Datamolino were not popular either. This could be attributed to restrictions in features, complexity in setting up, or compatibility with particular organizational sizes or technical capabilities. Similarly, applications such as Approval Max, MileIQ, Airwallex, Firstbase, HostBooks GST, myBooks, Socius, Tipalti, Airbase, Gaviti, and ADP Workforce Now evidenced little to zero adoption. Most of these resources were reported to have functionality restrictions, integration caps, or are built for targeted tasks instead of comprehensive accounting purposes.

While the table presents the most commonly used accounting software in the respondents' workplaces, it is important to note that the majority of them did not receive formal training in these software programs during their undergraduate studies as indicated by the questionnaire data. Among the 33 respondents, only one received

extensive training. Given this, most of them agreed that it is essential for accounting students to gain hands-on experience with accounting software before entering the workforce.

Advantages that BSA Graduates Have in Using Accounting Software in the Workplace

This section focuses on identifying the specific benefits of using accounting software in the workplaces of graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) program at Palawan State University. The initial results presented in this section reflect the advantages with the highest mean that is based on the data gathered from the respondents. Table 3 breaks down the agreeability of each statement.

Table 3
Advantages of Utilizing Accounting Software

Statement	<i>x</i>	Verbal Interpretation
It can increase efficiency and speed in completing tasks.	4.79	Very Advantageous
It can provide better access to and analysis of financial data.	4.64	Very Advantageous
It can ease reporting and presentation creation.	4.64	Very Advantageous
It can improve decision-making based on real-time data.	4.61	Very Advantageous
It can improve accuracy and reduction of error.	4.58	Very Advantageous
It can reduce manual labor and paperwork.	4.58	Very Advantageous
It can improve cost-effectiveness by reducing the need for manual.	4.58	Very Advantageous
It can improve performance in remote work or hybrid work setup.	4.55	Very Advantageous

Legend: 1.00-1.79 (Very Not Advantageous), 1.80-2.59 (Not Advantageous), 2.60-3.39 (Average), 3.40-4.19 (Advantageous), 4.20-5.00 (Very Advantageous)

The table presents the top five advantages of using accounting software, based on the highest mean scores among the 20 advantages listed in the survey questionnaires. The results indicate that the majority of respondents found accounting software to be very advantageous in improving work efficiency and task completion speed, as reflected by the highest mean score of 4.79. One respondent mentioned that their output increased due to the software, which allowed them to finish tasks faster and accomplish more within a limited time.

Additionally, the data reveals that respondents considered accounting software to be very advantageous in providing better access to and analysis of financial data, as well as in simplifying report and presentation creation. This advantage received a mean score of 4.64, suggesting that the software enables users to locate, interpret, and share financial information in a more organized and understandable format.

Another key benefit highlighted by respondents was its very advantageous effect on decision-making through access to real-time data, with a mean score of 4.61. The software was also viewed as very advantageous in enhancing accuracy, reducing errors, minimizing manual labor and paperwork, and improving cost-effectiveness by decreasing reliance on traditional bookkeeping tools, supported by a mean of 4.58.

Lastly, with a mean score of 4.55, respondents found that accounting software was very advantageous for productivity in remote or hybrid work settings. One respondent shared that whether working from home, in the office, or while traveling, accounting software enabled access to necessary financial data and allowed them to work efficiently even outside the traditional office environment.

These findings suggest that the majority of respondents viewed accounting software as either advantageous or very advantageous. Beyond its use in the workplace,

it also enhances the skills, knowledge, and competence of accounting graduates. This supports the findings of various studies (Baylon *et al.*, n.d.; Arcega *et al.*, 2015; Khoshabri *et al.*, 2025; Robinson, 2024; Pan & Seow, 2016), which affirm that the integration of accounting software in the workplace improves the quality of financial reporting. The software's capabilities in data analysis, task automation, and record management are transferable to professional settings, enhancing efficiency, speed, and accuracy while promoting collaboration and reducing the risk of human error.

Moreover, Khoshabri *et al.* (2025) emphasized that cloud accounting systems not only improve reporting quality but also streamline decision-making and compliance through automation, real-time updates, and advanced security features.

The findings also show that many respondents believe accounting software is advantageous in reducing manual labor, particularly in computing taxes and preparing financial statements. Features like electronic invoicing and e-reminders for overdue payments contribute to customer convenience and improved service delivery. This enhances operational efficiency and transparency while strengthening data security—safeguarding sensitive client information and internal records. These observations align with the studies by Morales (2024) and QNE Software Philippines (2019), which highlighted the role of digitalization in strengthening data protection and streamlining BIR compliance.

Accounting Software Programs that are Applicable for Integration in the BSA Curriculum at Palawan State University

The last section aims to identify which accounting software programs are most applicable for integration into the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) curriculum at Palawan State University. The data presented in this section reflects the

responses of selected respondents regarding accounting software recommendations and reasons why they would recommend the accounting software for curriculum integration to support the findings.

Would you recommend the accounting software you commonly used to be taught to BSA students in Palawan State University?

Figure 5
Recommendation to Teach Accounting Software in Palawan State University

The graph above indicates that 100% of respondents recommends the integration of accounting software utilized in their workplace into the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy BSA curriculum.

This findings support that emphasizes the growing demand for accounting professionals with technology expertise, particularly in data analytics and cloud-based software studies (LSU Alexandria Newsroom, 2023; Tagamolila, 2023; Tahil, 2024; Lee *et al.*, 2018; Dapiton and Gano-an, 2023; Meyer, 2021; Nickell and Chambers, 2022). This necessitates curriculum changes to integrate practical software training, aligning with evolving CPA requirements (AICPA and NASBA) and AACSB accreditation standards. Studies showcasing the successful integration of software like QuickBooks (Abou-Ei-Sood, 2024; Tahil, 2024) and the positive impact on student learning and employability further validate the study's conclusions.

Table 4.*Accounting Software Recommendation*

<i>Software</i>	<i>Sector</i>			<i>Total</i>
	<i>Government</i>	<i>Private</i>	<i>Public</i>	
QuickBooks	10	12	5	27
Microsoft Excel	11	9	5	25
Xero	8	9	5	22
Sap	4	8	3	15
Oracle NetSuite	2	5	2	9

The table above presents the accounting software preferred by the respondents, recommended for integration into the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) curriculum. As shown, QuickBooks received 27 recommendations out of 33, followed closely by Microsoft Excel with twenty-five (25) recommendations from the respondents. Xero received 22 recommendations, whereas SAP had 15. After that, Oracle received nine (9) recommendations.

The findings indicate QuickBooks is the most recommended accounting software because of its high functionality and how easily it works with other tools. This was also highlighted in a recent survey by The Milestone Team (2024). Supported by Tagamolila (2023) that most of the accountants in small business prefer it because it offers both cloud-based and offline versions. The offline version is preferred by businesses operating in a single location due to its advanced features and high customizability. QuickBooks Online, on the other hand, provides a secure, cloud-based platform with extensive features that support collaboration, integration with other software, and an end-to-end experience for finance professionals.

Followed by the most recommended accounting software, mainly because it is widely used and familiar to most accounting professionals. Aside from that, Microsoft

Excel offers accounting capabilities that are useful for easily analyzing and managing financial data making it more practical accounting software. Respondents highly recommend this software because it is a foundational part of accounting workflow and makes work more efficient and accurate, ease of use and more accessible. Also, the respondent noted that, although Microsoft Excel is often considered one of the most basic accounting software to be learned in the field, he pointed out that possessing a higher level of mastery over this software could contribute to exceptional work performance in the workplace. They suggested incorporating into the curriculum the Microsoft Excel, as it is already used in the existing curriculum.

Then, Xero may be attributed for its user-friendly features, including cash-based and accrual-based bookkeeping support. By its nature, it allows users to work in real-time remotely, which is very efficient because the accounting team can work anywhere, anytime. The respondent highly suggested that both QuickBooks and Xero be included in the curriculum such that students could be equipped to be effective employees, particularly if they are to work for foreign businesses.

The strong preference for Quickbooks, Microsoft Excel, and Xero may be attributed to their user-friendliness, accessibility, and high functionality within educational settings over more complex Accounting Software. The interview with one of the respondents supports the finding that QuickBooks, Xero, and Microsoft Excel were more frequently used in offices than other accounting software. Microsoft Excel is the most utilized in the Philippines, particularly with start-up firms. The respondent also mentioned that QuickBooks is notably used in the United States; Oracle NetSuite and Xero are popular in Australia.

Meanwhile, the lower preference for SAP and Oracle Netsuite could be influenced by factors such as their complexity, cost, or limited exposure in educational curricula (The Milestone Team, 2023). However, the preference for more sophisticated accounting software such as SAP and Oracle NetSuite amongst larger businesses needs consideration in the curriculum. As highlighted by The Milestone Team (2024), SAP and Oracle NetSuite are comprehensive accounting solutions offering extensive functionalities beneficial for students aiming for careers in large corporations, where these advanced features are commonly utilized. Therefore, including exposure to these powerful systems in advanced courses may be beneficial. A balanced curriculum should incorporate both the user-friendly, widely-accessible tools (QuickBooks, Xero, and Excel) preferred for immediate applicability and the advanced ERP systems (SAP and Oracle NetSuite) necessary for future career success in larger organizations. This multifaceted approach would best prepare BSA graduates for the diverse landscape of the Philippine accounting profession.

Table 5
Reasons for Recommendation

Reason	Sector			<i>f</i>
	<i>Government</i>	<i>Private</i>	<i>Public</i>	
<i>Enhancing Practical Skills</i>	9	12	4	25
<i>Relevance to Industry Needs</i>	10	10	3	23
<i>Ease of Use and Accessibility</i>	9	8	4	21
<i>Job Market Advantage</i>	8	9	2	19
<i>Improving Graduate Employability</i>	5	9	4	18

The table shows that Enhancing Practical Skills was the most frequent reason for recommending accounting software in the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy curriculum, with twenty-five (25) responses. This was followed by Relevance to Industry Needs with twenty-three (23) responses, Ease of Use and Accessibility with

twenty-one (21), Job Market Advantage with nineteen (19), and Improving Graduate Employability with eighteen (18) respondents selecting this reason.

Those students who studied accounting software during their undergraduate studies enhanced their career prospects, improved efficiency and accuracy in financial reporting, and increased employability (LSU Alexandria Newsroom, 2023; Tagamolila, 2023; Tahil, 2024; Lee *et al.*, 2018; Dapiton & Gano-an, 2023). This result demonstrates that exposure to real-world software applications is critical for effective academic training and future workplace success. Relevance to Industry Needs, Job Market Advantage, and Improving Graduate Employability emphasize the knowledge of the accounting software would offer an edge in securing employment opportunities and the awareness of students regarding modern accounting expectations. Especially, the importance of technological competence increases in the updated CPA licensure model (Nickell & Chambers, 2022), and the companies are looking for graduates who are already competent in automation, data management, and cybersecurity, Meyer (2021). Ease of use and Accessibility indicates user-friendly accounting software—such as Microsoft Excel, which, according to Lee *et al.* (2018) is a widely used accounting software that was consistent across different accounting areas (including audit, tax, advisory, and corporate) and across all experience levels, and QuickBooks, which demonstrated greater effectiveness when applied in practical settings, Tahil (2024)—encourage greater student engagement and facilitate learning.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the final discussion of the study, focusing on the key findings, conclusions, and recommendations derived from the research entitled *Accounting Software Used in the Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration*. It provides a comprehensive synthesis of the study's results, offering insights into the advantages of accounting software in the workplace and its implications for the integration of accounting software into the academic curriculum at Palawan State University.

Summary

This research aimed to identify the most commonly used accounting software among Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from Palawan State University (PSU) between 2016 and 2020, along with the advantages of using accounting software in the workplace. The findings of this study provided a basis for introducing core software skills into the BSA curriculum to bridge the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the accounting profession.

Demographic Profile

The demographic profile showed that most respondents graduated between 2016 and 2019, with the highest concentration in 2019. The majority currently practice in government and private sector roles. The results revealed that Microsoft Excel was the most commonly used accounting tool, followed by QuickBooks, Oracle NetSuite, and Xero. Despite the frequent use of accounting software in the workplace, a significant percentage of respondents reported not receiving any formal training in accounting

software during their college years. Nevertheless, all respondents recognized the importance of hands-on experience.

Furthermore, data showed that the most preferred accounting software among respondents is Microsoft Excel, followed by QuickBooks, with Xero being the next choice. Other software choices included SAP, Oracle NetSuite, and Sage, while MYOB, JuanTax, and NetSuite ERP had very few users.

Commonly Used Accounting Software

The primary factors that influenced the respondents in choosing their preferred accounting software include its features and functions, which were the most significant factor, followed by ease of use, which was also a key consideration. The availability of cloud-based solutions was another important factor, as well as cost, which was relevant for affordability. Integration with other software also played a role, as did its utilization in actual work and fieldwork, which proved important for practical application. Familiarity with the software from university studies was also a factor, though it was less significant compared to the others.

The study highlighted the numerous advantages of accounting software in workplace, such as increased efficiency and speed in task completion, improved accuracy and reduction of errors, and enhanced collaboration with colleagues. Additionally, respondents highlighted better access to and analysis of financial data, streamlined reporting and presentation creation, and improved client service and communication. The software also facilitates compliance with regulatory requirements, supports real-time data-driven decision-making, and reduces manual labor and paperwork. Other notable benefits include greater workplace satisfaction and job security, enhanced understanding of financial trends and forecasting, and reduced

training time for new employees. Furthermore, accounting software contributes to improved performance in remote or hybrid setups, increased security and protection of financial data, and better analysis of financial ratios and key performance indicators (KPIs). Respondents also recognized its role in enhancing competitiveness in the job market, enabling international or multi-currency transactions, and optimizing time management for meeting deadlines and deliverables. Lastly, the use of accounting software improves cost-effectiveness by reducing reliance on manual bookkeeping tools and minimizes dependency on technical support for financial reporting, making it a valuable asset in professional settings.

Recognizing the growing importance of accounting software, all respondents emphasized the need to integrate workplace-used accounting tools into the BSA curriculum. QuickBooks received the highest number of recommendations, followed closely by Microsoft Excel. Xero, SAP, Oracle NetSuite, MYOB, and JuanTax were also suggested, while NetSuite ERP and Google Sheets received minimal endorsements. The study underscores the necessity of equipping students with practical software skills to enhance their preparedness for the accounting profession.

Conclusion

This study examined the accounting software commonly used by Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from 2016 to 2020 and investigated how well the current curriculum equips students in using these accounting software. The results uncover significant discrepancies between curriculum instruction and industry requirements, highlighting the necessity for curriculum integration of applicable accounting software. The following conclusions summarize the key insights and implications derived from the research results.

The findings derived from the demographic profile of the respondent, specifically Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) graduates from 2016 to 2020 indicate that none are now employed in the academe sector. Such a result points to an evident preference of the graduates towards seeking employment within the other sectors of the accounting profession like private, government and public practice. The lack of respondents from the academe could be due to many factors, most notably the relatively lower salary grade for positions at the academe and the significant workload that repeats every term in the academe. All of these make the academe seem to have poor financial and career opportunities. Consequently, graduates seem to prefer industries that are seen to offer more stability, better pay, and better long-term career opportunities. This pattern is an indication of a larger trend in career choice among BSA graduates, one that values economic and professional development in informing their work choices.

The research findings confirm that Microsoft Excel is the most preferred accounting software among BSA graduates. Microsoft Excel's use is primarily because the program can be used universally within any country and industry. In contrast to other accounting software, which can be bounded by locality-based regulations or by functions of specific industries, Microsoft Excel can be put into practical use in a broad context of professional environment, whether private sector, government agencies, or public practice. Its capacity for independent operation also adds to its practicality, particularly for use in workplaces where the internet connection is poor.

The results also identify a huge gap in the existing accounting curriculum, however. While Microsoft Excel is still a core tool, it is the only piece of accounting software currently covered in the accounting curriculum of Palawan State University,

which only provides intermediate proficiency in the accounting software. This limited instruction results in students not gaining advanced skills or practical expertise in the software, which are commonly required in actual accounting positions. There is a glaring lack of exposure or training in more sophisticated and common accounting systems like QuickBooks, Oracle NetSuite, and Xero. Such a restriction in the course may delay graduates in fully adjusting to modern accounting technologies and practices in the workplace. Thus, incorporating more in-depth software training within the course curriculum is necessary to prepare future accounting professionals with the necessary skills in an even more technology-based profession.

The survey results suggest that although graduates have been given basic training and recognize the benefits of traditional accounting practices, these on their own are no longer adequate in addressing the changing demands of the modern workplace. The advances in technology, especially the incorporation of accounting software, have much improved workplace productivity and efficiency. While BSA graduates are taught to be effective in traditional accounting, the evidence indicates that this training should now be supplemented with technological expertise. Thus, the integration of advanced accounting technologies into academic curriculum and professional practice is necessary to produce highly capable and productive accounting professionals for today's dynamic and technology-based work settings.

The results of this study underscore the need for Palawan State University to reevaluate and enhance its current Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) curriculum. Unanimously, all the respondents suggested the introduction of commonly used accounting software within the academic curriculum of BSA students, acknowledging that there is a major deficiency in the current program. Although

Microsoft Excel is still an essential tool, the lack of structured training in other industry-standard accounting software identifies a serious area for improvement.

The results of the survey indicated that the majority of respondents highly recommend adding QuickBooks as part of the curriculum, considering it is one of the most used accounting systems by the business community. As an added exposure, other important platforms like Xero and additional expertise in Microsoft Excel would further develop students' practical skills. Preparation of students in these tools will not only bring academic education in line with present industry needs but also prepare future graduates to be better equipped to enter the workforce as a capable, job-ready professional.

Recommendations

The researchers aimed to strengthen proficiency in accounting software and ensure its systematic integration into both academic instruction and professional practice. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to the following to achieve these objectives:

1. Palawan State University may allot a budget for the purchase of computer laboratory, equipment, and accounting software to be used by Accountancy and Management Accounting students, since there are no existing laboratories to use. Therefore, these activities will enable students to develop and subsequently enhance their proficiency in accounting software, preparing them for real-world applications. Furthermore, the Department of Accountancy and Management Accounting is requested to review and revise the course descriptions for the following subjects under the BS Accountancy program to better align with evolving industry demands and technological advancements: (1) Living in the

IT Era and (2) IT Application Tools in Business with Data Analytics. The current course description does not align what students will need in the future. Updating these course descriptions will ensure that BS Accountancy students gain relevant exposure to modern accounting technologies, enhancing their competitiveness in the field and preparing them for industry-standard software applications.

2. The College may incorporate the application of accounting software for professional courses, especially the major accounting subjects (i.e., taxation, auditing, financial accounting, and management accounting) of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy students. This integration should be structured within laboratory-based coursework to provide students with hands-on experience in industry-standard software, reinforcing theoretical concepts with practical applications. Moreover, the results of the study indicated that BSA graduates from 2016 to 2020 recommended Microsoft Excel, QuickBooks, and Xero to be integrated into the curriculum, as shown in Table 4 of the study. The College must also advise the faculty, especially of the Department of Accountancy and Management Accounting, to blend the use of accounting software in their lessons to further enhance the accounting software proficiency of students.
3. The students of BS Accountancy are encouraged to actively participate in learning accounting software; not only does it help to strengthen and build their proficiency, but it can also bridge the gap between theoretical and real-world application. The students are highly recommended as well to carefully internalize and understand the use of the different accounting software and be vigilant of the future updates the software will incur. Moreover, not only does this serve as an opportunity for students, but it also prepares them for greater

employability and professional readiness. BSA students are advised to learn from external providers while studying the program to further enhance and expose themselves to the usage of various accounting software.

4. Future researchers are encouraged to delve into the possible correlation between the Excel proficiency of the BSA students and the accounting software commonly used by BSA graduates in the workplace. This may provide further insights into the extent to which fundamental Excel competencies affect the software employed in professional environments. Furthermore, it is highly recommended that future researchers investigate the impacts of accounting software proficiency on employment results, salary levels, and career progression.
5. Publication materials such as pamphlets in relation to this study are advised to be disseminated to the whole University for public awareness and knowledge (see Appendix E: Sample Output).

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APPENDIX "A"
PHOTO DOCUMENTATION

Figure 6
Compilation of Interpretation – 23 April 2025

Figure 7
Follow-up Interview with the Respondents – 27 April 2025

APPENDIX “B”
LETTERS AND OTHER COMMUNICATIONS

Republic of the Philippines
PALAWAN STATE UNIVERSITY
 COLLEGE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNTANCY

3 February 2025

DR. CHERYLL ANNE C. DATOR
 University Registrar
 This University

Approved

[Signature]
 UR 02.03.25

Dear Dr. Dator:

A warm greeting to your kind office.

We are the 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Accountancy student-researchers at Palawan State University. We are conducting a study entitled **Accounting Software Used in The Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration** as part of our requirements for the completion of this program.

The following are the primary objectives of this study:

1. Identify the profile of BSA graduates from Palawan State University in terms of:
 - a. year graduated; and
 - b. field practicing the profession;
2. Determine the most commonly used accounting software programs among BSA graduates;
3. Assess the specific advantages that BSA graduates experience in using accounting software in their workplaces; and
4. Develop recommendations for the integration of accounting software programs into the BSA curriculum at Palawan State University.

As part of the study, our team would like to **respectfully request the official list of graduates of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy from the academic years 2015-2016 to 2019-2020**. They will be invited to participate in answering the questionnaire and series of interview sessions, which involve answering a set of questions about their perception on the accounting software that is commonly used in the field of accountancy.

If you have any questions or need further clarification, feel free to contact us at 202220042@psu.palawan.edu.ph or +63 975 2026 182. You may also contact our research adviser, Dr. Rossana Paleza-Colendra at rcolendra@psu.palawan.edu.ph, for other concerns about our research.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

[Signature]
FRANZ BERNARD O. MERCADO
 Research Leader

[Signature]
 pls. facilitate.
[Signature]

Vision: An internationally recognized university that provides relevant and innovative education and research for lifelong learning and sustainable development.

Mission: The Palawan State University is committed to upgrade the people's quality of life by providing education opportunities through excellent instruction, research and innovation, extension, production services, and transnational collaborations.

Quality Policy: We Provide equal opportunities for relevant innovative and internationally recognized higher education programs and advanced studies for lifelong learning and sustainable development. We Strongly commit to deliver excellence in instruction, research, extension, and transnational programs in order to meet the increasing levels of stakeholder demand as well as statutory and regulatory requirements. The University shall continually monitor, review and upgrade its quality management system to ensure compliance with national and international standards and requirements.

Management System
 ISO 9001:2015
 www.tuv.com.ph

Palawan State University, Brgy. Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, 5300, Philippines
 ✉ cba@psu.palawan.edu.ph 🌐 www.psu.palawan.edu.ph

Received by *[Signature]*
 FRANZ BERNARD O. MERCADO

Feb. 19, 2025

3 February 2025

ANNY CLOVERIES M. GABAYAN, CPA
Acting University Accountant
This University

Approved. *[Signature]* 2/3/2025

Dear Ms. Gabayan:

A warm greeting to your kind office.

We are the 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Accountancy student-researchers at Palawan State University. We are conducting a study entitled **Accounting Software Used in The Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration** as part of our requirements for the completion of this program.

The following are the primary objectives of this study:

1. Identify the profile of BSA graduates from Palawan State University in terms of:
 - a. year graduated; and
 - b. field practicing the profession;
2. Determine the most commonly used accounting software programs among BSA graduates;
3. Assess the specific advantages that BSA graduates experience in using accounting software in their workplaces; and
4. Develop recommendations for the integration of accounting software programs into the BSA curriculum at Palawan State University.

As part of the study, our team would like to respectfully request the conduct of pilot testing of our research questionnaire to the Accounting Office of the Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus. They will be invited to participate in answering the questionnaire and series of interview sessions, which involve answering a set of questions about their perception on the accounting software that is commonly used in the field of accountancy.

If you have any questions or need further clarification, feel free to contact us at 202220042@psu.palawan.edu.ph or +63 975 2026 182. You may also contact our research adviser, Dr. Rossana Paleza-Colendra at rcolendra@psu.palawan.edu.ph, for other concerns about our research.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

[Signature]
FRANZ BERNARD O. MERCADO
Research Leader

[Faint, illegible text]

[Faint, illegible text]

APPENDIX “C”
FORMS AND CERTIFICATIONS

Republic of the Philippines
PALAWAN STATE UNIVERSITY
College of Business and Accountancy
Department of Accountancy and Management Accounting
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa 5300

LETTER OF CONSENT

22 June 2025

Dear Respondent,

A warm greeting to your kind office.

We are the 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Accountancy student-researchers at Palawan State University. We are conducting a study entitled **Accounting Software Used in The Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration** as part of our requirements for the completion of this program.

The following are the primary objectives of this study:

1. Identify the profile of BSA graduates from Palawan State University in terms of:
 - a. year graduated; and
 - b. field practicing the profession;
2. Determine the most commonly used accounting software programs among BSA graduates;
3. Assess the specific advantages that BSA graduates experience in using accounting software in their workplaces; and
4. Develop recommendations for the integration of accounting software programs into the BSA curriculum at Palawan State University.

As part of the study, our team would like to invite you to participate in answering a questionnaire and a series of interview sessions. Your participation will involve answering a set of questions about your perception on the accounting software that is commonly used in the field of accountancy. The interview will take less than an hour to complete and will be conducted either in person or through an electronic medium at a time that is convenient for you.

Participation and Confidentiality

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you may choose to withdraw at any point without any consequence. If you choose to participate, your responses will be kept strictly confidential. Your personal information will not be linked to your responses in any reports or publications resulting from this study. If you agree, we may record the interview for accuracy purposes, but only we will have access to the recordings. These recordings will be securely stored and destroyed after one year following the completion of the study.

Potential Risks and Benefits

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this study. The information you provide may help us better understand the accounting software commonly used in the workplace. However, there are no direct benefits to you for participating.

Contact Information

If you have any questions or need further clarification, feel free to contact us at **202220042@psu.palawan.edu.ph** or **+63 975 2026 182**. If you have any concerns regarding your rights as a participant, you may contact our research adviser, Dr. Rossana Paleza-Colendra at **rcolendra@psu.palawan.edu.ph**.

By signing this consent form, you agree to participate in the interview and allow your responses to be used for research purposes as outlined above.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

FRANZ BERNARD O. MERCADO
Research Leader

Consent Form

I, the undersigned, have read and understood the above information and voluntarily agree to participate in this research.

Participant's Name: _____
Signature: _____

Date: __ / __ / __

Republic of the Philippines
PALAWAN STATE UNIVERSITY

Office of the University Library

CERTIFICATE OF ANTI-PLAGIARISM

Vision

An internationally recognized university that provides relevant and innovative education and research for lifelong learning and sustainable development.

Mission

The Palawan State University is committed to upgrade the people's quality of life by providing education opportunities through excellent instruction, research and innovation, extension, production services, and transnational collaborations.

I certify that the research paper entitled: **“ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE USED IN THE WORKPLACE: BASIS FOR CURRICULUM INTEGRATION”** conducted by **CASTRO, MARIA ELIZABETH, DIVINAGRACIA, REANME, MANALO, KHAMER JUN, MANGOTARA, PRINCESS JAMIRA, MERCADO, FRANZ BERNARD, PERIA, LIEZEL JOY, ROQUE, HONEY JANE DARYL, SOTEA, MARK ROBERT, and VEGA, JOHN CARLO MIGUEL** of **BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN ACCOUNTANCY** has been checked against plagiarism using Turnitin with **10%** result based on the analysis of the report produced by the system.

CHRISTIAN ROBERT B. NALICA
Director, Library Services

Date: June 3, 2025

Attachment: Turnitin Plagiarism report

Palawan State University, Brgy. Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, 5300, Philippines

 library@psu.palawan.edu.ph

APPENDIX “D”
RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondents,

This research work is a survey on **Accounting Software Used in the Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration**. The questions are designed to gauge essential software skills into the BSA curriculum, bridging the gap between academic preparation and the demands of the modern accounting workplace. Please respond accurately and truthfully. Rest assured that all information supplied will be strictly confidential and will not be revealed under any circumstances. Thank you.

Castro, Maria Elizabeth F. et al.

The Researchers

Instructions: *Please indicate your response by marking whichever option is appropriate.*

Section 1. Demographic Information

Name (Optional): _____

1. When did you graduate from Palawan State University?

- 2016 2018 2020
 2017 2019

2. What sector or field of profession are you currently working in?

- Public Private Government Academic

Section 2. Accounting Software Used in the Workplace

3. Which accounting software have you used before at work? Please check all that applies.

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------------|---|
| <input type="radio"/> QuickBooks | <input type="radio"/> Odoo Accounting | <input type="radio"/> FirstBase |
| <input type="radio"/> Xero | <input type="radio"/> QNE Software | <input type="radio"/> HostBooks GST |
| <input type="radio"/> SAP | <input type="radio"/> HashMicro | <input type="radio"/> mybooks |
| <input type="radio"/> Sage | <input type="radio"/> MYOB | <input type="radio"/> Socius |
| <input type="radio"/> FreshBooks | <input type="radio"/> easyFS | <input type="radio"/> NetSuite ERP |
| <input type="radio"/> Zoho Books | <input type="radio"/> JuanTax | <input type="radio"/> Tipalti |
| <input type="radio"/> Oracle NetSuite | <input type="radio"/> AccountEdge Pro | <input type="radio"/> Airbase |
| <input type="radio"/> Wave | <input type="radio"/> Datamolino | <input type="radio"/> Gaviti |
| <input type="radio"/> Kashoo Cloud Accounting | <input type="radio"/> Approval Max | <input type="radio"/> ADP Workforce Now |
| <input type="radio"/> Acclivity Group, LLC | <input type="radio"/> MileIQ | <input type="radio"/> Others: _____ |
| <input type="radio"/> Microsoft Excel | <input type="radio"/> Airwallex | |

4. From your answers in question number 3, please state the level of difficulty of the said accounting software.

Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	Extremely Hard
4	Hard
3	Neutral
2	Easy
1	Extremely Easy

Accounting Software	5	4	3	2	1
QuickBooks					
Xero					
SAP					
Sage					
FreshBooks					
Zoho Books					
Oracle NetSuite					
Wave					
Kashoo Cloud Accounting					
Acclivity Group, LLC					
Microsoft Excel					
Odoo Accounting					
QNE Software					
HashMicro					
MYOB					

Accounting Software	5	4	3	2	1
easyFS					
JuanTax					
AccountEdge Pro					
Datamolino					
Approval Max					
MileIQ					
Airwallex					
FirstBase					
HostBooks GST					
mybooks					
Socius					
NetSuite ERP					
Tipalti					
Airbase					
Gaviti					
ADP Workforce Now					
Others: _____					

5. How frequent do you use this accounting software?

Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	Daily
4	Several times a week
3	Once a week
2	Rarely
1	Never

Accounting Software	5	4	3	2	1
QuickBooks					
Xero					
SAP					
Sage					
FreshBooks					
Zoho Books					
Oracle NetSuite					
Wave					
Kashoo Cloud Accounting					
Acclivity Group, LLC					
Microsoft Excel					
Odoo Accounting					
QNE Software					
HashMicro					
MYOB					
easyFS					
JuanTax					

Accounting Software	5	4	3	2	1
AccountEdge Pro					
Datamolino					
Approval Max					
MileIQ					
Airwallex					
FirstBase					
HostBooks GST					
mybooks					
Socius					
NetSuite ERP					
Tipalti					
Airbase					
Gaviti					
ADP Workforce Now					
Others: _____					

6. Where did you first learn the accounting software you use at your work?

Scale	Descriptive Rating
1	During my undergraduate studies
2	On-the-job training provided by my employer
3	Online courses or certification
4	Self-taught
5	Other methods

Accounting Software	1	2	3	4	5
QuickBooks					
Xero					
SAP					
Sage					
FreshBooks					
Zoho Books					
Oracle NetSuite					
Wave					
Kashoo Cloud Accounting					
Acclivity Group, LLC					
Microsoft Excel					
Odoo Accounting					
QNE Software					
HashMicro					
MYOB					
easyFS					
JuanTax					

Accounting Software	1	2	3	4	5
AccountEdge Pro					
Datamolino					
Approval Max					
MileIQ					
Airwallex					
FirstBase					
HostBooks GST					
mybooks					
Socius					
NetSuite ERP					
Tipalti					
Airbase					
Gaviti					
ADP Workforce Now					
Others: _____					

7. Did you receive any formal training on accounting software during your college days?
- Yes, extensive training
 - Yes, some training
 - No, I did not receive any training
8. How important do you think it is for accounting students to have hands-on experience with accounting software before entering the workforce?
- Very important
 - Important
 - Neutral
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all

9. Which accounting software would you recommend or prefer to use at your work?
Please check all that applies.

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------------|---|
| <input type="radio"/> QuickBooks | <input type="radio"/> Odoo Accounting | <input type="radio"/> FirstBase |
| <input type="radio"/> Xero | <input type="radio"/> QNE Software | <input type="radio"/> HostBooks GST |
| <input type="radio"/> SAP | <input type="radio"/> HashMicro | <input type="radio"/> mybooks |
| <input type="radio"/> Sage | <input type="radio"/> MYOB | <input type="radio"/> Socius |
| <input type="radio"/> FreshBooks | <input type="radio"/> easyFS | <input type="radio"/> NetSuite ERP |
| <input type="radio"/> Zoho Books | <input type="radio"/> JuanTax | <input type="radio"/> Tipalti |
| <input type="radio"/> Oracle NetSuite | <input type="radio"/> AccountEdge Pro | <input type="radio"/> Airbase |
| <input type="radio"/> Wave | <input type="radio"/> Datamolino | <input type="radio"/> Gaviti |
| <input type="radio"/> Kashoo Cloud Accounting | <input type="radio"/> Approval Max | <input type="radio"/> ADP Workforce Now |
| <input type="radio"/> Acclivity Group, LLC | <input type="radio"/> MileIQ | <input type="radio"/> Others: _____ |
| <input type="radio"/> Microsoft Excel | <input type="radio"/> Airwallex | |

10. What factors influenced your decision to choose a particular accounting software?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Cost | <input type="radio"/> Recommendations from colleagues or mentors |
| <input type="radio"/> Ease of use | <input type="radio"/> Availability of cloud-based solutions |
| <input type="radio"/> Features and functionalities | <input type="radio"/> Compliance with industry regulations (e.g., tax reporting) |
| <input type="radio"/> Integration with other software (e.g., payroll, inventory) | <input type="radio"/> Others: _____ |
| <input type="radio"/> Training and support available | |
| <input type="radio"/> Familiarity with the software from university studies | |

Section 3. Advantages of Accounting Software

Instructions: From your own perspective, please indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Scale	Descriptive Rating
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Neutral
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Statement	5	4	3	2	1
1. It can increase efficiency and speed in completing tasks.					
2. It can improve accuracy and reduction of errors.					
3. It can enhance collaboration with colleagues.					
4. It can provide better access to and analysis of financial data.					
5. It can ease reporting and presentation creation.					
6. It can improve client service and communication.					
7. It can enhance ability to meet regulatory requirements.					
8. It can improve decision-making based on real-time data.					
9. It can reduce manual labor and paperwork.					
10. It can increase workplace satisfaction and job security.					
11. It can enhance understanding of financial trends and forecasting.					
12. It can reduce training time required for new accounting employees.					
13. It can improve performance in remote work or hybrid work setup.					

14. It can increase security and protection of financial data.					
15. It can improve ability to analyze financial ratios and KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).					
16. It can improve competitiveness in the job market.					
17. It can increase ability to handle international or multi-currency transactions.					
18. It can better time management for meeting deadlines and deliverables.					
19. It can improve cost-effectiveness by reducing the need for manual bookkeeping tools.					
20. It can reduce dependency on external technical support for financial reporting.					

Section 4. Accounting Software Recommendation

1. Would you recommend the accounting software you commonly used to be taught to BSA students in Palawan State University?

Yes

No

2. What accounting software would you recommend being taught in Palawan State University? Please check all that applies.

QuickBooks

Odoo Accounting

FirstBase

Xero

QNE Software

HostBooks GST

SAP

HashMicro

mybooks

Sage

MYOB

Socius

FreshBooks

easyFS

NetSuite ERP

Zoho Books

JuanTax

Tipalti

Oracle NetSuite

AccountEdge Pro

Airbase

Wave

Datamolino

Gaviti

Kashoo Cloud Accounting

Approval Max

ADP Workforce Now

Acclivity Group, LLC

MileIQ

Others: _____

Microsoft Excel

Airwallex

3. Why would you recommend the said accounting software to be taught in Palawan State University?

- Ease of Use and Accessibility
- Enhancing Practical Skills
- Cloud-Based Features
- Academic Benefits
- Relevance to Industry Needs
- Cost-Effectiveness
- Improving Graduate Employability
- Others, please specify: _____
- Curriculum Relevance
- Job Market Advantage
- Adaptability to Various Business Sizes
- Bridging Academic Knowledge and Practice
- Preparation for Certification Exams
- Essential Foundational Tool

PILOT TESTING FEASIBILITY AND READINESS FEEDBACK FORM

Thank you for answering the pilot questionnaire for the study **Accounting Software Used in the Workplace: Basis for Curriculum Integration**. Our team will do our best to improve for the betterment of the study. In line with this, attached to the questionnaire is the pilot testing feasibility and readiness feedback form for your convenience. Please answer the questions truthfully. Please note that answering this form is optional, and you may opt out of answering the said form.

Participant's Name (Optional): _____

Date: _____

Instructions: Please check the answer that you deem appropriate.

<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
5	4	3	2	1

Statement	5	4	3	2	1
The questionnaire can assess the experiences of BSA graduates about the use of accounting software in their workplace.					
Each statement is clear and concise.					
The questionnaire is appropriate.					
The statements and questions are easy to understand.					
The questionnaire can make the participants feel comfortable and engaged.					
The questions and statements are free from flaws.					
The questions and statements are well-constructed.					
The questions and statements do not violate the privacy of the respondent.					
The questionnaire considers ethics in formulating the questions and statements.					

Do you have any suggestions for improving the questionnaire provided? Are there any parts that needs to be added or removed?

Please share any other feedback or thoughts regarding the questionnaire provided.

Thank you for answering the form!

Vision: An internationally recognized university that provides relevant and innovative education and research for lifelong learning and sustainable development.

Mission: The Palawan State University is committed to upgrade the people's quality of life by providing education opportunities through excellent instruction, research and innovation, extension, production services, and transnational collaborations.

Quality Policy: We Provide equal opportunities for relevant innovative, and internationally recognized higher education programs and advanced studies for lifelong learning and sustainable development. We Strongly commit to deliver excellence in instruction, research, extension, and transnational programs in order to meet the increasing levels of stakeholder demand as well as statutory and regulatory requirements. The University shall continually monitor, review, and upgrade its quality management system to ensure compliance with national and international standards and requirements.

APPENDIX “E”
SAMPLE OUTPUT

Microsoft Excel
is the most widely used software tool, considered essential for new hires, and needed priority in university accounting courses. The experience of Microsoft Excel sets a clear pattern across various accounting fields, such as audit, tax, advisory, and corporate, and across all levels of experience (Gue et al., 2010).

FEATURES:
Built-in formulae for quick calculations and data analysis.
Charting tools to visualize trends and patterns.
Summaries and visualizes financial data.
Ready-made sheets for income, balance, and cash flow.
Real-time editing with others via OneDrive.

ADVANTAGES:
Enhances practical skills.
Increases relevance to industry needs.
Offers ease of use and accessibility.
Real-time financial highlights.
Cost Management and Structure.
Regulatory Issue.
Provides a job market advantage.
Improves graduate employability.

Quickbooks
is the most recognized and popular accounting software, especially among SMEs. QuickBooks has a robust system and an offline version, and is preferred by businesses working in one location only since it allows high customization and advanced features. Due to its security and complexity, it has remained the choice for companies whose accounting needs are more diverse than others (The Milestone team, 2023; Logarithm, 2023).

FEATURES:
Tracks income, expenses, and bank transactions automatically.
Tracks accounts receivable management.
Tracks sales levels, costs, and sales.
Reporting and analytics.
Automates tax calculations and supports e-filing.
General ledger.
Cloud access.

ADVANTAGES:
Enhances practical skills.
Increases relevance to industry needs.
Offers ease of use and accessibility.
Provides good accounting reports.
Robust features set.
Provides a job market advantage.
Improves graduate employability.

Oracle NetSuite
is an accounting software solution for companies in outsourcing and managing financial matters through its great Financial Management Features (Milestone, 2025).

FEATURES:
Financial Management Modules.
Manages customer relationships and sales data.
Provides online resources and business operations.
Inventory, Order, Supply Chain & Procurement Management.

ADVANTAGES:
Enhances practical skills.
Increases relevance to industry needs.
Offers ease of use and accessibility.
Comprehensive Features.
Provides a job market advantage.
Improves graduate employability.

Current Practice: While accounting software aligned with Philippine Financial Reporting Standards (PFRS) and Philippine Accounting Standards (PAS) works, its usage among graduates is minimal. Microsoft Excel is often used as a makeshift accounting system.

Learning Curve: The difficulty in learning these software varies depending on prior exposure and training.

Commonly Used Software:

- Microsoft Excel
- QuickBooks
- Oracle NetSuite

Research conducted by:
Cristo Rina Duran P., Development, Nurine G.
Marilyn Reyes J., Management, Denise James L.
Melinda Scott Bernard G., Data Lead, Pia D.
Ryssa, Hilda, Jane Dora P., Denise Mary Roban V.
Faye John Carlo Mager C.

Advisor: Dr. Rosemarie Palanca-Cabrera
Department of Accounting and Management
Accounting, Palawan State University
May 2023

Figure 8
Publication Materials – Pamphlet

APPENDIX “F”
CURRICULUM VITAE

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Maria Elizabeth Francisco
Castro**

Student ID : **2022-2-0155**

Sex : **Female**

Status : **Single**

Date of Birth : **6 October 2003**

Place of Birth : **Puerto Princesa City**

Parents : **Maria Magiena B. Francisco
Basilio A. Castro**

Email Address : **202220155@psu.palawan.edu.ph**

Cellphone Number : **0912 100 1661**

Address : **Manalo St., Tanglaw, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **East Central School**
Palanca St., Puerto Princesa City
2010 – 2016

Secondary : **Palawan National School**
H. Mendoza St., Puerto Princesa City
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Reanne Gorospe Divinagracia**
Student ID : **2022-2-0582**
Sex : **Female**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **21 February 2004**
Place of Birth : **Roxas, Palawan**
Parents : **Gina Gorospe**
Ryan Divinagracia
Email Address : **202220582@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0970 144 8115**
Address : **Purok Kaakbayan, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Andres Soriano Memorial Elementary School**
Roxas, Palawan
2010 – 2016
Secondary : **Roxas National Comprehensive High School**
Roxas, Palawan
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)
Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Khamer Jun Lugo Manalo**
Student ID : **2022-2-0035**
Sex : **Male**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **30 October 2004**
Place of Birth : **Antipuluan, Narra, Palawan**
Parents : **Lucita Itumon Lugo**
Jun Rosas Manalo
Email Address : **202220035@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0975 202 6182**
Address : **Zabala St., Purok Centro, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Tarusan Elementary School**
Tarusan, Bataraza, Palawan
2014 – 2016

Secondary : **Tarusan National High School**
Narra-Narra, Tarusan, Bataraza, Palawan
2016 – 2020 (Junior High)

Mandaragat-San Miguel Senior High School
Old Buncag Road, Mandaragat, Puerto Princesa City
2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Princess Jamira Sevilla**
Mangotara

Student ID : **2022-2-0469**

Sex : **Female**

Status : **Single**

Date of Birth : **3 March 2004**

Place of Birth : **Puerto Princesa City**

Parents : **Jenifer S. Sevilla**
Armodin M. Mangotara

Email Address : **202220469@psu.palawan.edu.ph**

Cellphone Number : **0970 144 8115**

Address : **Solid Rd., Purok Pagbabago, San Manuel, Puerto**
Princesa City

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Puerto Princesa Pilot Elementary School**
Rizal Ave., Puerto Princesa City
2009 – 2016

Secondary : **Palawan National School**
H. Mendoza St., Puerto Princesa City
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Franz Bernard Orog Mercado**
Student ID : **2022-2-0042**
Sex : **Male**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **18 November 2003**
Place of Birth : **Puerto Princesa City**
Parents : **Daisy Regis Orog**
Remigio Vilorio Mercado
Email Address : **202220042@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0948 144 4854**
Address : **Binuatan HOA, Purok Firetree, Sicsican, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Palawan Adventist School**
55 Fernandez St., Tanglaw, Puerto Princesa City
2011 – 2016

Secondary : **Palawan Adventist School**
55 Fernandez St., Tanglaw, Puerto Princesa City
2016 – 2020 (Junior High)

Palawan National School
H. Mendoza St., Puerto Princesa City
2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Liezel Joy Degillo Peria**
Student ID : **2022-2-0005**
Sex : **Female**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **5 April 2004**
Place of Birth : **Puerto Princesa City**
Parents : **Elnora G. Degillo**
Leo A. Peria
Email Address : **202220005@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0906 611 3184**
Address : **Lomboy St. Carlou Ville, San Jose, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **East Central School**
Palanca St., Puerto Princesa City
2010 – 2016

Secondary : **Palawan National School**
H. Mendoza St., Puerto Princesa City
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Honey Jane Daryl Perez Roque**
Student ID : **2022-2-0245**
Sex : **Female**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **23 January 2004**
Place of Birth : **Bataraza, Palawan**
Parents : **Roselyn Autida Perez**
Edgar Eustaquio Roque
Email Address : **202220245@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0955 517 8036**
Address : **Liberty Rd., Bagong Sikat, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Bataraza Central School**
Bataraza, Palawan
2012 – 2016

Secondary : **Bataraza National High School**
Bataraza, Palawan
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **Mark Robert Vasquez Sotea**
Student ID : **2022-2-0187**
Sex : **Male**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **31 December 2003**
Place of Birth : **Pangobilian, Brooke's Point,
Palawan**
Parents : **Maricell Alim Vasquez
Roberto Magbanua Sotea**
Email Address : **202220187@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0977 470 2149**
Address : **Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Pulot National High School**
Pulot Center, Sofronio Española, Palawan
c. 2010 – c. 2016

Secondary : **Pulot National High School**
Pulot Center, Sofronio Española, Palawan
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tiniguiban Campus**
Tiniguiban Heights, Tiniguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : **John Carlo Miguel Cahilig Vega**
Student ID : **2022-2-0320**
Sex : **Male**
Status : **Single**
Date of Birth : **17 January 2004**
Place of Birth : **Mandaluyong City**
Parent : **Pamela Cahilig Vega**
Email Address : **202220320@psu.palawan.edu.ph**
Cellphone Number : **0946 712 4060**
Address : **Tinguiban, Puerto Princesa City**

Educational Attainment

Primary : **Narra Pilot School**
Rizal Ave., Poblacion, Narra, Palawan
2011 – 2016

Secondary : **Narra Integrated School**
Omayao Rd., Narra, Palawan
2016 – 2020 (Junior High); 2020 – 2022 (Senior High)

Tertiary: : **Palawan State University – Tinguiban Campus**
Tinguiban Heights, Tinguiban, Puerto Princesa City
2022 – present